

D4.3: Benchmarking Initial Report

Grant Agreement n°. 101084234

**Funded by
the European Union**

VERSION HISTORY

Ver.	Date	Comments/Changes	Author/Reviewer
0.1	4.12.2024	Working draft version	Galway and ECOLISE
0.2	10.12.2024	Updated working draft version	Galway and ECOLISE
0.3	17.12.2024	Full working draft	Galway and ECOLISE
1.0	24.12.2024	Final version	Galway and ECOLISE/Consortium

DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

Project Acronym	FLIARA
Project Title	FLIARA: Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas
Type of action	HORIZON-RIA
Topic	HORIZON-CL6-2022-COMMUNITIES-01-01
Project Start Date	01/01/2023
Project Duration	36 months
Work Package	WP4: FLIARA Community of Practice Network
Deliverable	D4.3: Benchmarking Initial Report
Due Date	31/12/2024
Submission Date	24/12/2024
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Deliverable Responsible	ECOLISE and University of Galway
Version	1.0
Status	Final version
Author(s)	Aisling Murtagh, Anastasia Oprea, Maura Farrell, Louise Weir
Contributor(s) - WP3 Case Study Policy Assessments:	<i>Czech Republic:</i> Antonín Vaishar; <i>Finland:</i> Simo Sarkki, Tuomas Kuhmonen, Belyta Tembo, Hannu Heikkinen; <i>Germany:</i> Felicia van Tulder; <i>Ireland:</i> Aisling Murtagh, Maura Farrell, Louise Weir <i>Italy:</i> Irene Leonardelli, Silvia Sivini; <i>Romania:</i> Anastasia Oprea, Laura Incze; <i>Slovenia:</i> Sara Mikolič, Irma Potočnik Slavič; <i>Spain:</i> Víctor Martínez, Michelle Perello <i>Sweden:</i> Helene Ahl, Annie Roos; <i>The Netherlands:</i> , Vitnarae Kang.
Reviewer(s)	Helene Ahl, Hannu Heikkinen, Laura Incze, Vitnarae Kang, Willem Korthals Altes, Annie Roos, Silvia Sivini, Gerdy Verschuure-Stuip, Susanne von Münchhausen

¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

List of Tables	5
Acronyms and Abbreviations	7
Key highlights	9
1. Introduction	11
2. Building on FLIARA's Policy and Legal Framework Assessment.....	13
2.1 Insights for benchmarking from promising policy developments	13
2.2 Policy gaps and areas for policy improvement	19
2.3 Wider Reflections on issues for future policy.....	27
2.4 Conclusion	28
3. Building on the FLIARA women-led innovation case studies	29
3.1 Farm innovation case studies: Emerging future policy needs and promising developments	29
3.2 Rural Innovation case studies: Emerging future policy needs and promising developments	47
3.3 Case Study Conclusions: A wish list of future policy needs?.....	62
4. Focus groups on policy benchmarking and policy design	64
4.1 Existing Support for Rural and Agriculture Women-led Innovation: Promising Developments and Future Needs	65
4.2 Challenges Related to Rural Services and Societal trends	68
4.3 What appear as the most critical issues for future policy to address?	74
4.4 Conclusion and Specific suggestions for policy.....	77
5. Key issues for the next CoP policy design and assessment workshops	79
5.1 Cross-cutting issues.....	79
5.2 Issues related to specific barriers to Women-led rural and farm innovation	83
5.3 Conclusion	85
6. Key benchmarking findings.....	87

6.1 Some reflections on the initial good practice policy benchmark statements	87
6.2 Wider guidelines for next steps	90
6.3 Other reflections on policy benchmarking	92
7. Conclusion and next steps.....	94
References	95
Annex 1: Focus group and case study policy assessment methodology	97
Annex 2: Initial good practice benchmark statements.....	99
Annex 3: Operationalising a benchmarking statement? One outline example	100

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Potential benchmarks for assessing LEADER on its gender equality performance	16
Table 2: Potential benchmarks: Selection criteria prioritise support for women	18
Table 3: Potential benchmarks: Supporting better representation of women in a range of areas of rural life.....	20
Table 4: Potential benchmarks: Supporting women-led rural and farm entrepreneurship through knowledge, networks and skills development	21
Table 5: Potential benchmarks: Supporting women-led rural and farm entrepreneurship through access to finance.....	22
Table 6: Potential benchmarks: Policies that address supports that more indirectly facilitate women-led innovation without direct targeting.....	25
Table 7: Potential benchmarks: Facilitating rural and farm women-led innovators to balance all of life's commitments	26
Table 8: Innovation and enterprise support system: Ideas for potential benchmarks and examples from case study assessments	32
Table 9: Access to finance: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments	35
Table 10: Access to land: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments	37
Table 11: Support system: Idea for potential benchmark and examples from case study assessments	40
Table 12: Supporting renewal of the farm economy and women-led innovation: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments.....	42
Table 13: Tackling gender norms and gender related barriers: Ideas for potential benchmarks from the case study assessments	44
Table 14: Addressing work-life issues: Ideas for potential benchmarks from the case study assessments.....	46
Table 15: Better supporting women-led entrepreneurial innovation: Ideas for potential benchmarks and examples from case study assessments.....	49
Table 16: Access to finance for women-led rural innovation: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments	52

Table 17: Support system: Idea for potential benchmark and examples from case study assessments	54
Table 18: Supporting renewal of the rural economy and women-led innovation: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments.....	55
Table 19: Tackling gender norms and gender related barriers in rural areas: Ideas for potential benchmarks from the case study assessments.....	58
Table 20: Addressing rural services and work-life issues: Ideas for potential benchmarks from the case study assessments	61
Table 21: Aspirational policy wishes emerging from the women-led farm and rural innovation case studies	62
Table 22: Potential benchmarks for assessing public policies regarding women innovating sustainably in agriculture.....	66
Table 23: Potential benchmarks for assessing public policies regarding mobility in rural areas	69
Table 24: Potential benchmarks for assessing public policies regarding access to information about relevant funding and entrepreneurship opportunities for women.....	72
Table 25: Potential benchmarks for agriculture, rural development and entrepreneurship policy impact assessment on women, rural women and young rural	77
Table 26. Policy suggestions of the innovative women as shared during the CoP workshops	77
Table 27: Definitions of methods of gender-related policy assessment	91

ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CoP	Community of Practice
CSP	CAP Strategic Plan
EC	European Commission
EIGE	European Institute for Gender Equality
EU	European Union
LAG	Local Action Group
LTVRA	Long Term Vision for Rural Areas
PMEF	Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework
SO8	Specific Objective 8
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
SWOT	Strength, Weakness, Opportunity, Threat
UNDROP	United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Peasants and Other People Working in Rural Areas: resolution / adopted by the Human Rights Council on 28 September 2018
WP	Work Package
Project Partners	
Galway	NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND GALWAY
TU Delft	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
TEAGASC	TEAGASC - AGRICULTURE AND FOOD DEVELOPMENT AUTHORITY
UNICAL	UNIVERSITA DELLA CALABRIA
LWL	LONGFORD WOMEN S LINK CLG

Funded by
the European Union

UTU	TURUN YLIOPISTO
UL	UNIVERZA V LJUBLJANI
CE	CONSULTA EUROPA PROJECTS AND INNOVATION SL
HNEE	HOCHSCHULE FUR NACHHALTIGE ENTWICKLUNG EBERSWALDE
ELARD	ASSOCIATION EUROPEENNE LEADER POUR LE DEVELOPPEMENT RURAL
UOULU	OULUN YLIOPISTO
ECOLISE	RESEAU EUROPEEN POUR DES INITIATIVES COMMUNAUTAIRES SUR LES CHANGEMENTS CLIMATIQUES ET LE DEVELOPPEMENT DURABLE
MENDELU	MENDELOVA UNIVERZITA V BRNE
LNU	LINNEUNIVERSITETET
HLK	HOGSKOLAN FOR LARANDE OCH KOMMUNIKATION I JONKOPING - HLK SCHOOL OF EDUCATION AND COMMUNICATION, JÖNKÖPING UNIVERSITY

KEY HIGHLIGHTS

This report draws together different types of FLIARA evidence - a policy and law assessment, case study findings and Community of Practice (CoP) workshops - to identify key policy issues to be brought forward and further explored by FLIARA, but also to help shape developing the FLIARA benchmarking guidelines for assessing policies supporting women-led rural and farm innovation. Two key sections draw together the findings:

- **Section 5** focuses on the key policy issues and needs identified in this report.
- **Section 6** focuses on the more specific emerging issues in relation to developing a benchmarking framework.

To attempt to draw together the range of evidence and insights presented in this report, four key high-level needs are outlined below, as well as more specific policy needs and issues that benchmarking should consider.

Address social and cultural conditions impacting women-led rural and farm innovation through:

- Innovative policy measures need to work to address gender stereotypes, traditional gender norms and patriarchal attitudes.
- Measures need to tackle improving the visibility and recognition of existing women-led innovation.
- Policies need to effectively address the challenge of balancing all of life's demands, such as parental leave, enabling innovators to take holiday leave and benefit from remote business and work opportunities.

Address barriers in the policy support system itself that hinder women leading rural and farm innovation benefiting as best possible from existing supports through:

- Greater attention is given to the policy life cycle, looking at issues in policy design that impact effective delivery and uptake of support measures.
- Policy governance also receives greater attention, and spaces are strengthened that enable women's improved participation in the decisions that impact women-led rural and farm innovation.

Strengthen the conditions for women-led rural and farm innovation and entrepreneurship through improved supports:

- Women-led rural and farm innovation needs to be supported to flourish through a diverse range of supports that address women's needs such as improved access to finance, networks, knowledge and skills development opportunities.

**Funded by
the European Union**

- Within the support system, specific needs also need to be addressed, such as targeted supports to different stages of the innovation journey and the needs of particular groups of women.

Strengthen rural and farm economy renewal and sustainability with women-led innovation as a lever:

- Women-led rural and farm innovation appears to embed an untapped opportunity for wider benefits to enhance the rural and farm economy. This calls for certain areas to receive improved supports, such as social, cultural, environmental and digital rural and farm innovation.
- Alongside this, there is a need for more policies that are integrated, place-based and locally led.

1. INTRODUCTION

This report starts the process of drawing together the FLIARA findings to inform the project's policy design and assessment activities that take place in Work Package (WP) 5. It emerges from Task 4.3 of FLIARA WP4 that aims to build on the results of WP1 and WP3, as well as presenting the outcomes of the focus groups on benchmarking held at the CoP events in Ireland and Slovenia as part of WP4.

A comprehensive range of data and analysis is drawn together in this report. It is not an exhaustive assessment of all policies and policy needs relating to women-led rural and farm innovation, however this report does provide another key part of our foundational knowledge base to shape FLIARA's policy related tasks. The report identifies policy relevant insights for benchmarking but also wider issues, such as potential promising practices, emerging policy needs and improvement opportunities.

This report most directly aims to feed into our WP5 'Gender Benchmarking Report' (D5.3) that will provide a set of final guidelines for gender benchmarking. The EC's 100 Words For Equality defines benchmarking as: "The establishment of criterion, standard or reference point against which to establish targets and measure progress" (EC, 1998, p. 13). Benchmarking is a useful process to identify good practices and room for improvement in policy. However, it faces an enormous challenge to determine the criteria or indicators to be used to benchmark. FLIARA's benchmarking activities take a three-phase process and are designed with this challenge in mind. This report brings together different types of data (policy analysis, case study results and CoP workshop findings) to identify key issues for consideration and potential indicators for benchmarking. This report sits in the middle of the FLIARA three step process that underpins the project's benchmarking activities.

Firstly, as part of WP1 FLIARA assessed policy and legal frameworks that directly and indirectly support women-led rural and farm innovation (D1.3). This resulted in a substantial inventory of relevant public policy and legal frameworks for all ten FLIARA partner countries. This then fed into the development of Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking (D1.5).

Secondly, this report represents the middle step. It explores a key issue highlighted in the FLIARA report 'Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking' (D1.5). This was if we wish to benchmark policy, we must establish what the benchmark is. This is a core question underpinning this report.

- Each of the main parts (Section 2, 3 and 4) contain tables highlighting 'targeted actions' that provide information to help inform the benchmarks to be outlined in our final Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3).
- **Section 2** draws further insights from the assessment of policy and legal frameworks and how they directly and indirectly support women-led rural and

farm innovation reported on in D1.3, also drawing out some wider insights for benchmarking.

- **Section 3** contains the results of a specific targeted analysis of the WP3 rural and farm women-led innovation case studies carried out for this report to identify key policy relevant results.
- **Section 4** reports on the benchmarking and policy design workshops held at the CoP events in Ireland and Slovenia. The CoP provides a space for the multi-actor approach to be applied, engaging women innovators, policy makers and other key stakeholders in the FLIARA benchmarking activities. Further details on the methodology underpinning Section 3 and 4 are also presented in Annex 1.
- **Section 5** identifies key issues to be brought forward and explored at the focus groups on benchmarking and policy design due to be held at the upcoming CoP events in Italy and Sweden as part of WP4.
- **Section 6** explores wider insights and questions for further consideration for developing a benchmarking framework.

Thirdly, emerging from Work Package 5, the final 'Gender Benchmarking Report' (D5.3) will follow on from this report. There is still further work to do to pool and draw together the results of this report. Our final Gender Benchmarking Report will also include a review and outline the state of current gender benchmarking. All of this evidence combined will then allow FLIARA to develop a set of final guidelines for gender benchmarking policy in relation to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.

2. BUILDING ON FLIARA'S POLICY AND LEGAL FRAMEWORK ASSESSMENT

Benchmarks can be determined from existing good practice policy measures that support improved levels of women-led rural and farm innovation. However, deriving benchmarks from existing policy alone is not an effective approach when there are still gaps and room for improvement in how policy supports women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. This is why FLIARA draws together case study and CoP workshop findings in this report. That said, assessing existing policy is still a key, central and essential part of how benchmarks are determined. The final FLIARA benchmarking guidelines will therefore incorporate strengths currently seen in policy, as well as gaps and improvements called for in the FLIARA research.

Throughout this section tables highlight various measures identified from national assessments that could act as benchmarks to assess policy on its gender equality performance in relation to supporting women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. This is intended to provide a useful basis of information for FLIARA's next and final benchmarking report (D5.3) where the final benchmarking guidelines will be presented.

Promising policy developments are also broadly discussed in this section, as well as inherent complexities in the policy process that are wider points of debate. None of the promising policy developments can be presented as a 'good practice' but do represent areas of particular interest, such as recent advancements in how policy begins to better focus on gender equality (e.g. CAP Specific Objective 8), as well as long-established promising policies, however that could also be improved to better support women-led innovation (e.g. The LEADER Programme). We also discuss wider policy gaps and areas for policy improvement. In this section we also reflect directly on drawing out broad insights and key takeaways for policy benchmarking that can help inform the final benchmarking guidelines focused on in our next deliverable D5.3.

2.1 INSIGHTS FOR BENCHMARKING FROM PROMISING POLICY DEVELOPMENTS

Recent policies show elements of promise. However, the complexity of policy processes raise a range of issues linked to for example policy design, implementation, monitoring, impact assessment and governance. After discussing key areas, some insights and takeaways for benchmarking are also outlined. CAP is a key EU policy influencing farming and rural development. National CAP Strategic Plans (CSPs) guide implementation at the Member State level. It is a key policy discussed in this section, but also potentially merits further deeper assessment. For example, we discuss the LEADER Programme below, but not the EIP-AGRI or AKIS measures that are important when it comes to innovation support. These measures could need further reflection as part of WP5 and this will be considered in our next steps.

Inclusion of gender equality in CAP 2023-2027 S08

At the European level progress is seen with reference in Specific Objective 8 (S08) of CAP 2023-2027 to enhancing gender equality in rural areas, including the position of women in farming. However, from national assessments the filtering down to measures supporting improved gender equality in rural areas and farming is not widespread across Member States. This is seen from the FLIARA policy and legal framework assessment (Murtagh et al. 2024a, hereafter referred to as D1.3) and others (e.g. EC, 2022). Member States are recommended by the EC to include targeted measures in CSPs to address the specific needs of women in agriculture and rural areas as well as to ensure that gender equality in the agricultural sector is strengthened (EC, 2020). CAP 2023-2027 should also direct support to those most in need. One area of identified need, as clear from its inclusion in SO8, is improving gender balance in farming. The system of prioritising needs means that if gender equality in agriculture is seen as the most pressing need targeted measures linked to SO8 must be more robust and effectively implemented. But CSPs have many needs to prioritise which perhaps has seen the needs of rural and farm women, as well as the issues of gender equality in farming slipping down the priority scale. For example, in Ireland's policy and law assessment (see D1.3) the need to increase opportunities for women in agriculture and business development is identified as the sixth highest priority of six other priorities (so the lowest ranked) as part of SO8. In Italy's policy and law assessment (see D1.3) the identification of needs presents a long list of 50 needs. Two mention women, but alongside youth, and these needs are not classified as high priority. Generally, it is observed that in relation to SO8 young people and women are targeted together and regions are encouraged to adopt preferential selection criteria for these groups. In Romania's policy and law assessment (see D1.3) it is noted that in the CSP the need to support gender equality by better involving the female population in entrepreneurship is identified as a moderate need, but it is only partly addressed. Addressing SO8 does not include measures directly targeting women in agriculture or rural areas and justifies this by stating women can benefit from sector specific interventions. In summary, even when some needs are identified and measures included, the eventual focus on women and supports that materialise can be residual.

The CSP recommendations made by the EC to MS also note that particular attention needs to be paid to "provision of good quality childcare services in rural areas and to closing gender gaps, in particular in employment" (EC 2020, p.14). However, this point is made in the context of more innovative ways fund support measures and using the CAP alongside other European policies, funds, private resources and initiatives to address structural challenges and create more favourable dynamics in rural areas (EC 2020). Better collaboration across funds is a potential mechanism to ensure issues, such as those related to gender equality, can be better addressed rather than falling down the priority list of issues to address in one policy. For example, in Spain's policy and law assessment (see D1.3) part of the approach is to coordinate CAP with other EU funding sources, such as the Recovery and Resilience Facility and the European Structural and Investment Funds to strengthen the overall support system. There is scope to better

understand if this approach better leverages the goals emerging from multiple policies to ensure farm and rural women's specific needs and gender equality issues do not get de-prioritised.

The FLIARA policy and legal framework assessment (D1.3) also highlights how the monitoring and evaluation of S08 through the European Commission's Performance Monitoring and Evaluation Framework (PMEF) for CAP does not include specific result indicators related to gender equality and just one impact indicator mentions gender, by gathering a gender breakdown: "Contributing to jobs in rural areas: Evolution of the employment rate in rural areas, including a gender breakdown" (EU, 2021). The monitoring and evaluation data generated in relation to S08 indicators appears weak in terms of what it can reveal on gender equality achievements.

Key benchmarking insights:

- **Policy Process:** It is important that policy benchmarking on gender equality in relation to women-led innovation occurs at different stages of the policy process (programming, implementation, monitoring, evaluation) and not just in relation to policy promises at one governance level. This is particularly true in the case of EU policy because of the complex policy activities and processes between the EU, Member State, regional and local levels. What is promising at one point (e.g. S08) may be partly or completely lost at another (CSPs). Result indicators are particularly important to include the monitoring of gender data to allow for benchmarking, as well as wider policy monitoring and evaluation to understand the results of policy measures from a gender perspective.
- **Policy Monitoring and Data:** Better availability of data opens new venues for gender benchmarking of policy. Including a gender breakdown in an increased number of indicators in policy monitoring frameworks would provide more detailed information around the gender balance of uptake of particular measures. Particularly when gender equality is part of overarching objectives its funnelling through to the monitoring framework also appears a key part of understanding how well this particular aspect of the objective is achieved.

LEADER Programme directly supports innovation

LEADER is an important programme to support rural innovation. The FLIARA policy assessment (D1.3) noted further analysis was still needed (e.g. through assessment of Local Development Plans) to truly understand its impact on supporting women-led innovation. It did however find that direct targeting of LEADER support in CSPs towards women-led innovation was not found in most national assessments. Where it was, a range of different examples (see Table 1) can be identified and are potentially useful to inform future benchmarking.

Table 1: Potential benchmarks for assessing LEADER on its gender equality performance

Targeted action	Examples
Gender mainstreaming is applied	The design and implementation of Local Development Strategies in Sweden must align with Sweden's gender mainstreaming policy. Similarly in Germany there is strategic gender mainstreaming in the LEADER approach. Finland also implements gender mainstreaming.
Measures are taken to support better representation of women in LEADER Local Action Groups (LAGs)	In Romania, LAGs must have one organisation representing women's interests involved. In addition, at least 30% of representatives must be young or female. In Ireland a diversity of local actors and gender balanced representation must be aimed for in LAGs.
Gender equality is an assessment criteria to assess proposed Local Development Strategies	In Italy gender equality is among the criteria used to assess the quality of proposed Local Development Strategies in some Italian regions. In Slovenia supporting women is included within the selection criteria for assessing Local Development Strategies and awarded 2 out of 16 overall points.
Specific calls for LEADER funding are made targeting women.	In Ireland and Italy there is room potentially for targeted calls for LEADER funding that could specifically target women. In Romania, 244 of 246 LAGs included operations with an economic purpose whose direct beneficiaries are women and/or young people (between 18 and 30 years old) in their 2023-2027 strategies. However two LAGs exclusively targeted women as direct beneficiaries.
Addressing the needs of rural women are part of Local Development Strategies	In Sweden in the 2014-2020 period improving levels of women's entrepreneurship was a goal in some Local Development Plans.
National guidelines for LEADER implementation include recommendations on how to address the needs of rural women	The Romanian LEADER Strategic Development Guidelines for 2023-2027 include measures to increase women's role in rural economic development. In Ireland, the LEADER Programme Operating Rules 2023-2027 recommend an increased focus on supporting female entrepreneurs under the wider theme of enterprise development.

More broadly, LEADER was still observed to be a potential strong support and have further potential to support women-led rural and farm innovation. The LEADER method gives it this advantage through its bottom-up, community-led approach to address local needs in rural development. National assessments described how the LEADER method builds social capital meaning there is added value in the approach in addition to the supports it provides. However, the assessment also notes that if there is not a direct and targeted focus on women and innovation this creates potential variability and uncertainty around the level of support for women-led innovation. The point is also made that if

women are not targeted directly, monitoring the impact of LEADER on women-led innovation and more broadly improving gender equality becomes doubly important.

More broadly too, room for improvement was also noted. Research on LEADER in Spain for example noted that positive discrimination is not enough to achieve gender equality in LEADER project funding. Wider issues are noted to impact women-led enterprise, such as women's preference for certain sectors due to reconciling family commitments and sometimes a need for large investments (Cejudo et al., 2020). An EC evaluation of LEADER observed that LEADER's strength in supporting gender equality is potentially more to improve socio-economic opportunities for women (e.g. support women entrepreneurs) rather than address women's social exclusion. That said, the evaluation also noted that projects with gender equality goals can be classified under other categories (e.g. disadvantaged groups, culture, education) hence impacts are potentially under reported.

Another strength of the LEADER method is its delivery through Local Action Groups, however the issue of under-representation of certain groups, including women, is observed (e.g. ECA, 2022). National assessments (D1.3) found some national level measures working towards addressing this (see Table 1 above). Further to this, the EC (2024) taking stock of the LTVRA actions notes that in some CSPs women's participation in LEADER is incentivised, but also that LEADER budgets must do more with less because absolute budgets have not increased.

Key benchmarking insights:

- **Policy Methods:** The existence of some policy methods (bottom up versus top down) can potentially increase the chances of addressing specific local barriers to women-led innovation and improved gender equality in rural and farming contexts. That is however if gender equality issues and barriers to women-led innovation are issues identified locally. The FLIARA policy assessment (D1.3) noted that LAGs can be a key driver of issues identified locally. Hence a focus on measures to support better representation of women in LAGs is an important part of realising the value of the LEADER method in addressing rural and farm gender equality issues and an important part of benchmarking.
- **Policy Design:** Targeting supports or positive discrimination in policy design appears an important part of improving women-led farm and rural innovation. However, applying for LEADER funding itself requires specific capacities, including a time commitment and navigating the application process. Capacity building and ensuring potential women innovators have the capacity to apply for LEADER funding is also important to ensure access to LEADER supports. A potential benchmark is therefore if local capacity building activities target vulnerable groups, including women.
- **Policy Monitoring and Data:** The benchmarks identified in Table 1 present a starting point and represent promising developments in LEADER's direct focus on gender equality. However, they are by no means comprehensive and potentially there is a need for the development of a set of common data indicators

to benchmark LEADER on gender equality performance at national levels. This does not just mean including a gender breakdown in relevant data collection (e.g. jobs created) but also should include wider indicators related to gender equality and important monitoring of softer outcomes (e.g. networking opportunities created, training supplied).

Selection criteria ensure women are prioritised for support

A pattern identified in some of the policies assessed as part of D1.3 was that rather than targeting support directly towards women at the outset, an alternative way to prioritise women for support is in how applications for support were assessed. This involves specific assessment criteria for support being applied, often involving allocating extra points to women applicants. The Slovenian policy assessment highlights this approach in a number of the CAP 2023-2027 interventions and also as part of the LEADER Programme. Italy also emerges as taking this approach (see Table 2). This approach is not without criticism, however. The Slovenian policy assessment also notes that the 2017-2014 CAP and Rural Development Programme in Slovenia included measures that targeted women exclusively, but also that issues around fairness and equity for all were concerns raised in relation to this. This approach of course is not fitting in some countries, such as Sweden and Finland, where gender equality laws and policy do not generally allow for prioritisation a particular gender.

Table 2: Potential benchmarks: Selection criteria prioritise support for women

Targeted action	Examples
Young women farmers are prioritised for support as part of generational renewal measures	In Slovenia, the CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027 intervention to support the establishment of young farmers' businesses women receive an additional 3 points in the selection criteria.
Addressing gender equality is prioritised in the selection of LAGs and Local Development Strategies	As already outlined in Table 1 above, in Italy (some regions) and Slovenia this type of approach is taken. For example, in Slovenia selection criteria for assessing Local Development Strategies awards supporting women 2 out of 16 overall points.
Supporting women's enterprise is a priority area for support as part of a wider non-targeted enterprise support scheme.	In Italy, the CAP 2023-2027 intervention on investments in agricultural holdings for diversification into non-agricultural activities supporting women's enterprise is included as a priority (alongside young people) as part of the beneficiary selection criteria.

2.2 POLICY GAPS AND AREAS FOR POLICY IMPROVEMENT

Issues impacting women-led rural and farm innovation are diverse and this raises a range of areas in need of attention in relation to potential for policy improvement. For example the EC (2024) taking stock of the Long Term Vision for Rural Areas (LTVRA) actions note broadly in relation to CSPs there is a need for greater attention to connectivity, social inclusion, rural business and innovation. In this section we draw together some key areas emerging from the FLIARA policy assessment (D1.3) and reflect on the potential benchmarks this suggests for policy.

Address under-representation of women in a range of areas of rural life

In the development of CAP strategic plans SWOT analyses identify needs to support the intervention logic of the CSP in each country. Underrepresentation of women in farming is already an acknowledged area of need through the inclusion of promoting the participation of women in farming in S08. However, the SWOTs in a number of countries identify wider areas where women are underrepresented, and this provides a good snapshot of key issues:

- **Farming and other areas of the rural economy:** The low share of women in farming, but also forestry and fishing sectors highlighted in Ireland's CSP.
- **Managerial positions:** In Romania's CSP gender imbalances are highlighted in agricultural and forestry managerial positions. In Ireland's CSP generally significant underrepresentation of women in management roles is identified.
- **Land ownership and inheritance:** Levels of female farm succession and land inheritance are issues highlighted in Ireland's CSP. In Sweden the CSP SWOT highlights how women are highly underrepresented as landowners.
- **Decision making:** In Spain's SWOT a significant weakness identified is the low presence of women in decision making bodies as a significant weakness. Sweden's SWOT highlights women's underrepresentation on company board membership.

Generally wider issues are also highlighted in the FLIARA policy assessment (D1.3), such as more broadly the need to improve rural women's labour market participation and participation in politics. The FLIARA policy assessment (D1.3) also identified some promising measures that work to address underrepresentation of women in different areas. Table 3 presents an overview of such actions. These also include policy measures, initiatives and projects that are not targeted directly to support women, nor women in rural areas and farming. Nevertheless, they are areas where women are thought to benefit or address issues impacting women and could provide ideas for actions to be adapted to address more specific issues in women-led rural and farm innovation.

Table 3: Potential benchmarks: Supporting better representation of women in a range of areas of rural life

Targeted action	Examples from national assessments
Measures exist to support gender balance in particular economic sectors where women are under-represented	In Ireland's policy assessment targeted support programmes to encourage careers for women in STEM sectors and engineering (e.g. THRIVE, Athena STEM and EXPLORE Engineering Alliance) are identified. In Italy the National Strategy for Gender Equality includes a range of supports for better women's participation in STEM such as scholarships, strengthening education guidance services and reserving places in courses in STEM disciplines. Innovation policy in Finland has a focus on working to remove stereotypes in education and employment and promoting possibilities for women's education in traditionally male sectors.
Measures exist to support gender balance in politics	Gender quotas for electoral lists exist in Ireland, Slovenia, Italy, and Spain and is a practice by many political parties in Sweden. Visibility of women in politics is highlighted in Germany through prizes such as the Helene Weber Prize for recognition of outstanding achievements in local politics. The See Her Elected Programme in Ireland supports rural women engage in local democracy through the provision of training, mentoring and networking.
Measures exist to support gender balance on the boards of enterprises	In Italy there is a law on the representation of women on the board of directors and auditors of listed companies, as well as non-listed companies controlled by public companies. There is a quota in place and amendments have increased this from an initial 20% in 2011 to now 40%.
Measures to increase and promote acceptance of remote working	Remote work is presented as an opportunity to support better female labour market participation. In Finland the National Rural Policy Programme includes proposals to increase acceptance of remote work as it is intended to open possibilities for women's labour market participation. In Italy the National Strategy for Gender Equality includes a measure to allow for additional flexibility of remote working for parents with dependent children, but with certain age requirements for qualification.
Policy dialogues on gender issues in rural areas and farming (led by Government) are being run and actions are being developed based on these dialogues	The Irish government facilitated a National Dialogue on Women in Agriculture. The first National Dialogue in 2023 generated a 12-point Women in Agriculture Action Plan. The Women in Agriculture Working Group guides implementation of the action plan.
Official spaces exist where issues related to women in agriculture	In Slovenia, the Rural Women's Council is an advisory body within the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food and

and rural areas are communicated to government and acted upon	provides opinions and input on key decisions relating to women in rural areas.
---	--

Strengthen the conditions for women-led rural and farm entrepreneurship

Strengthening the conditions for women-led entrepreneurship is important to better support women-led innovation. The FLIARA policy assessment (D1.3) identified a range of examples of targeted supports towards women’s enterprise, but more often than not these examples were not targeted towards women-led innovation in rural or farm contexts. Nevertheless, a diverse range of targeted examples did emerge from our assessment that provide a basis for potential benchmarking of policy supports on its gender equality performance in relation to supporting women-led rural and farm innovation. In the tables that follow examples are drawn together around two key important themes that are identified. The first is supports that build knowledge, networks and skills. The second is access to finance, such as grants, tax credits and low-cost finance. The ‘targeted actions’ refer to rural enterprise, but this set of potential benchmarks could be adapted to also focus solely on, or also on farm enterprise, to more clearly account for these distinctions. Table 4 draws together a range of examples related to knowledge, networks and skills development for women-led enterprise. Some of these actions focus specifically on start-ups, which raises a question about the need for benchmarks that tap into other stages of the women-led innovation journey.

Table 4: Potential benchmarks: Supporting women-led rural and farm entrepreneurship through knowledge, networks and skills development

Targeted action	Examples
Women-led rural entrepreneurship training programme exists	In Spain, the Rural Women Advancement Programme has a focus on entrepreneurship and innovation and supports women through training and mentoring. The EIT Food programme Empowering Women in Agrifood supports early-stage women-led business develop their entrepreneurial path. This is an EU co-funded program implemented in several Member States.
Women-led rural entrepreneurship training programme exists focused on increasing women’s participation in sectors they are under-represented	While not focused on rural women, in Italy as part of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan one of its female entrepreneurship programmes aims to generate a female entrepreneurial culture and includes a focus on scientific and technological fields.
Women-led rural business networking supports exist	In Ireland the Women’s Rural Entrepreneurial Network targets self-employed women, start-up or established women entrepreneurs. It is a local scheme run by LAGs in county Cork and Limerick.

Women-led rural business mentoring programme exists	ACORNS is peer-led support network for rural female entrepreneurs in Ireland. The focus is on helping nascent start-ups accelerate their establishment and development.
Support exists for women-led rural business organisations	In Slovenia the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men includes an action on strengthening the role of women in agriculture. This helps to support organisations that assist with for example networking and knowledge provision such as the Association of Farming Women of Slovenia.

Table 5 focuses on the important area of access to finance. Many of these finance supports do not target a particular stage of business development, hence are potentially open to any stage. One of the actions focuses specifically on start-ups. Nevertheless, the lack of specific focus on post-start-up business development does again raise the question of the need for supports to better target stages of the women-led innovation journey. It is also notable among the grant supports that 100% funding is not provided, but a percentage of the investment costs are supported by grants meaning match funding is required by applicants. Match funding is a considerable issue for women who may have limited access to resources and fewer investors or funding opportunities.

Table 5: Potential benchmarks: Supporting women-led rural and farm entrepreneurship through access to finance

Targeted action	Examples
Access to finance: Innovative women-led rural enterprise grants exist (part-funding, non-repayable)	In Italy the Innovative Mountain Women's Enterprise scheme finances investment in women-led business projects with high technological and innovative content in mountain municipalities by providing a non-repayable grant for up to 70% of eligible expenses and to a maximum of €70,000.
Access to finance: Innovative women-led rural enterprise fund low cost (or interest free) finance exists	In Italy, the ISMEA (Institute of Services for the Agricultural Food Market) scheme 'More Enterprise - Youth and Women Entrepreneurship in Agriculture' provides interest free finance to women (and young people) intending to take over a farm or have done so in the previous two years, providing support for business expansion and improving competitiveness.
Access to finance: Innovative women-led rural enterprise tax credit exists	While not targeting women directly, in Italy under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan incentives are included for tourism enterprises including Agri-tourism and a tax credit is available covering up to 80% of eligible expenses.

Access to finance: Innovative women-led rural enterprise Guarantee Fund for Bank Credit exists	While not targeting rural women directly, in Italy the Guarantee Fund for SME supports access to bank finance (with limits) through state guarantee and includes a special section for female enterprises.
Access to finance: Higher grant rates are available to rural women (part-funding, non-repayable) as part of a wider support scheme for rural business	In Ireland the CAP the On-Farm Capital Investment Scheme supports increased farm efficiency and competitiveness by providing financial support to farmers. Grants are provided to cover 40% of costs however female and young farmers can claim 60% of the costs (up to a maximum investment ceiling).
Access to finance: Low cost (or interest free) finance exists for innovative women-led start-ups	In Italy, Smart & Start Italia supports the creation and development of innovative start-ups financing projects between €100,000 and €1.5 million with interest-free, guaranteed financing that covers 80% of eligible expenses, but up to 90% for women only start-ups.

Prioritising policies that address women’s specific needs, barriers and opportunities

Need for a better focus on gender norms and stereotypes

Gender related barriers and opportunities are discussed in more depth in Section 3 of this report that draws out policy issues from the FLIARA rural and farm women-led innovation case studies. However, from the FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3) some more specific gender-related issues can be pinpointed as barriers to women-led innovation that gain some attention through policy, as well as point to areas in need of improved attention through policy. The persistence of patriarchal norms and attitudes emerges as an issue. For example, the need to address patriarchal mindsets is highlighted in Romania’s CSP. More widely in Czechia men as breadwinners and women as caregivers is noted as a preconception that persists. The issue of persisting gendered stereotypes in career choices is also noted. The German CSP notes that there is an opportunity in breaking the role of stereotypes in career choices. Ireland’s CSP notes the persistence of the perception of farming as a male occupation. These issues can also be part of the influences impacting under-representation of women in a range of areas of rural life (as discussed above). Addressing these issues through specific policy measures was not however identified directly as part of the FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3) and appears an important policy gap needing attention. Benchmarking therefore also needs to consider how to determine indicators to measure and compare levels of policy action.

Need for a focus on barriers and opportunities faced by particular groups of women

Addressing the needs and capitalising on opportunities for women-led innovation focused on the needs of different groups of women, but alongside women in different types of rural places, appears an important policy gap needing attention. In relation to Cohesion Policy, specific groups of rural women and women in different types of rural

places are noted in a European Parliament resolution to potentially have different effects on cohesion. The resolution points to the importance of young women to rural cohesion and more broadly women in remote areas for their contributions to sustainable growth. However, it is also noted that this comes with barriers to overcome to realise this potential (European Parliament, 2022). The FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3) found that young women farmers were sometimes a focus in policy. In Italy, support for both youth and women's entrepreneurship in agriculture is identified, such as availability of non-repayable grants and interest free finance. However, another important point identified was that at the time of our assessment funds were exhausted and meaning supports could not be applied for. Greater focus is seen in how CAP results are measured through the existence of the CAP result indicator on generational renewal. It records the 'Number of young farmers benefitting from setting up with support from the CAP 2023-2027, including a gender breakdown'. In Slovenia, young women farmers are prioritised for support as part of generational renewal measures, as highlighted above in Table 2 above. However, these appear isolated examples and there is significant room for further progress in this area. This appears an important area of attention for benchmarking to start to assess the extent of policy practice in this area.

The FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3) also identified a lack of focus on other groups of women in policy. One example that emerged was from Sweden where Sami women are directly targeted in the National Food Strategy due to their position as traditional knowledge holders in Sami food and this is in need of preservation. In the German CSP in relation to SO8 and across all objectives, gender equality and the inclusion of all social groups serves as a cross-cutting task and also as a high priority issue, but the trickle down in terms of specific interventions addressing this is confined to certain federal states. Another area of potential relevance relates to women that experience social exclusion face specific barriers and these potentially also impact women-led innovation. Policy that brings together targeting issues of social exclusion and assisting rural and farm women to start or develop innovations was not strongly identified in the FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3). There are some examples identified of wider laws of relevance to reducing rural women's social exclusion. One example is Slovenia's National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men that includes an action relating to reducing poverty risk and social exclusion of the most vulnerable groups of women, with rural women one group highlighted. This also appears an important area that benchmarking needs to consider and compare levels of policy action.

Potential room for attention to particular policy areas to assess indirect support

The FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3) also identifies some opportunities related to particular areas of farming and the rural economy where women can more readily become innovators. Support for practices that tap into farm diversification opportunities and developing the multifunctional aspects of farming, as well as a more diverse rural economy are pointed to as indirectly supporting women-led farm and rural innovation without being a directly targeted support. Specific agricultural practices such as organic farming and wider farm-related activities such as care farming and Agri-tourism are

examples. One example of specific laws in this area identified in the FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3) is the discussion of laws in Italy that focus on social agriculture, agritourism and organic farming. Supports that facilitate short food supply chains are also discussed. There is greater room to further identify and assess these types of supports in relation to their place in supporting improved levels of women-led rural and farm innovation. The FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3) points to the potential importance of including measures relating to these areas to assess indirect supports for women-led rural and farm innovation. If benchmarking then aims to more comprehensively compare the support system the targeted actions identified in Table 6 then become potential areas to derive benchmarks.

Table 6: Potential benchmarks: Policies that address supports that more indirectly facilitate women-led innovation without direct targeting

Targeted action	Examples
A supportive policy framework exists for multi-functional farming e.g. sectors such as short food supply chains; care/social farming; agritourism; organic agriculture	In Italy a law exists to regulate establishing farmers' markets and wider spaces dedicated to farm product sale.
A supportive policy framework exists for a more diversified rural economy e.g. sectors such as digital innovation, creative industries; social enterprise and rural tourism	The Rural Innovation and Development Fund provides part-funding grants for projects in the Irish context and includes an agri-food tourism measure and provides grants to part fund projects. The National Strategy for Sustainable Regional Development in Sweden focuses on supporting innovation and takes a particular focus on microbusiness and social entrepreneurship.
Supports exist to facilitate women-led farm diversification	The On-Farm Capital Investment Scheme in Ireland and Spain's National Plan for the Application of Agricultural Technologies could support farm diversification projects. Other measures in this table, such as the above mentioned Rural Innovation and Development Fund could also support farm diversification.
Supports exist to facilitate women-led rural enterprise capitalise on digital transformation	While not targeting rural women directly, in Spain the National Plan for the Application of Agricultural Technologies aims to support the integration of advanced technologies in farming such as areas like precision agriculture, biotechnology, and wider digital solutions.
Action Plan for Women in Rural Business exists	While not targeted towards rural areas or farming, in Ireland the Enterprise Ireland Action Plan for Women in Business works to increase the representation of women in enterprise.
Place-based funds have a focus on supporting women-led rural innovation	In Italy the Innovative Mountain Women's Enterprise scheme finances investment in women-led business projects with high technological and innovative content.

Policies supporting work-life balance impact innovation capacity

Rural service provision, such as public transport, childcare, as well as policies that support balancing work and life demands were considered as part of FLIARA’s policy and law assessment (D1.3). Rural and farm women-led innovation does not occur in isolation from daily life. Services and supports that help to ensure women are not overburdened with demands created by either their innovation directly or the commitments and challenges they must balance as part of their lives in general are important to assess in relation to how women can be better supported in rural and farm innovation. For example, the FLIARA Knowledge Review (D1.2) highlights how women are understood to devote a greater proportion of their time to care and domestic commitments than men. This makes services such as childcare important to influence women’s potential to devote their capacities to innovation. Table 7 below draws together some examples of policy areas that merit greater attention in relation to supporting women-led rural and farm innovation, as well as areas that appear to need space and consideration when it comes to policy benchmarking.

Table 7: Potential benchmarks: Facilitating rural and farm women-led innovators to balance all of life’s commitments

Targeted action	Examples
Family leave schemes enable the sharing of leave entitlements among parents	The birth and care of a minor leave in Spain gives both parents entitlements to maternity leave. In Sweden both parents are also entitled to paid parental leave and there is no specific maternity leave. Parents have 480 days of parental leave to share.
Childcare places are guaranteed for pre-school children	In Sweden children from age one are guaranteed a childcare place.
Childcare costs are minimal or free	In Sweden the cost of childcare is very low with the highest fee payable €150 per month per child. In Slovenia an income assessed subsidy system across 10 income groups exists which can result in childcare payments varying from 0% to 77% of the full price.
Farmers are supported to take paid holiday leave through a publicly funded scheme	In Finland holiday leave for farmers is supported under a publicly funded farm relief scheme and covers the cost of temporary workers. The scheme allows for parental leave and pregnancy leave.
Supports exist to facilitate entrepreneurs take on employees	In Sweden business owners can gain subsidies towards employing a person with a disability, health issues, in long-term unemployment or has newly immigrated.

2.3 WIDER REFLECTIONS ON ISSUES FOR FUTURE POLICY

In this section we reflect on some wider issues emerging from FLIARA's policy and law assessment (D1.3) that have potential insights to gain from in relation to devising a framework for benchmarking policy in relation to supporting women-led rural and farm innovation.

Questioning the effectiveness of addressing gender equality as a cross-cutting policy action

The route from policy to action is a complex one. Policy can focus on gender equality in different ways. For example, in the 2021-2027 period gender equality is a cross-cutting horizontal principle part of the Cohesion Policy funds, apart from ESF+ where there is a specific objective focused on women's labour market participant and improving work-life balance. The cross-cutting principle approach has been criticised as making gender equality less prominent meaning it is addressed too generally and needs a more targeted approach (GENDERACTION, 2021; D'Ambrogio, 2023). If this cross-cutting approach is taken the key importance of looking beyond the programming phase and also to implementation, monitoring and evaluation phases in assessing the impact of this policy on gender equality is highlighted (D'Ambrogio, 2023). In Germany the CSP includes gender equality and the inclusion of all social groups as a cross-cutting task and high priority issue with two specific interventions explicitly linked to this. However, focus on these is confined to certain Federal States rather than a widespread action.

To target or not to target

The earlier discussion in this section highlighted examples of actions that target women directly. For instance, there are a range of potential actions detailed in Table 4 that outline examples of measures supporting women-led rural and farm entrepreneurship through knowledge, networks and skills development. However, in some countries, due to specific laws, differentiation between genders in this way is not an approach immediately taken. For example, in Finland, under the Act on Equality between Women and Men there is a duty on authorities to promote gender equality, but this is done in a purposeful and systematic way. This means authorities must create and consolidate administrative and operating practices to ensure equality between women and men is advanced, both in the preparatory work undertaken on different matters and in decision-making. If there are circumstances that prevent achieving gender equality changes must be made. In the FLIARA policy and law assessment (D1.3) Sweden also points to the general gender equality policy that exists there which means all policies are subject to gender mainstreaming. Gender equality must be considered at all levels and at each step in the policy process. This also means there is a general absence of specific policies supporting women in farming and rural areas. This raises an issue for benchmarking if we wish to include countries with and without these types of laws in the same benchmarking exercise. It also raises a more systematic and wider issue of how to tackle gender equality issues through policy. The FLIARA Conceptual Framework (D1.1) argued however that the: "pathway to gender equality needs to be built on equity to balance the

opportunities available for women and men. Given the existing inequalities in rural innovation, affirmative governance should provide additional opportunities and advantages to women until women can 'level the playing field' in relation to innovation" (Farrell et al., 2023, p.7-8, D1.1).

The strength of wider policy impacting rural development and farming also influences women-led innovation

Issues impacting women-led rural and farm innovation are diverse. They cross into different policy domains such as entrepreneurship and family policies. This raises a range of areas in need of attention when we assess the potential for policy improvement and the need to look beyond traditional spaces of rural development and farming policy. This is acknowledged by the EC for example in the EC (2024) taking stock of the LTVRA actions. This assessment notes the need for better support for rural women in a range of areas: "facilitating their access to funding, providing diverse and flexible employment and training and educational opportunities, and involving them in policy design and in local decision-making processes" (EC, 2024, p. 15). The scope of the FLIARA policy assessment was expanded beyond our initial aims as outlined in the project proposal to assess policy and law related to farming and rural development. This was also driven by the FLIARA Conceptual Framework (D1.1) that understands women-led innovation as occurring part of an innovation ecosystem. There is also an innovation journey within this that follows a pathway with a number of steps. Identifying benchmarks across a diverse range of relevant policy domains add to the complexity of the policy benchmarking challenge in the women-led rural and farm innovation context. It also raises potential need for benchmarking to take a more focused approach. Rather than just take a more generalised approach to benchmarking focusing benchmarking activities on particular policy area or key topics (e.g. access to finance or access to networks) is important to consider.

2.4 CONCLUSION

What is outlined in this section needs further assessment regarding how the potential benchmarks can work in the practice of benchmarking policy. Further thinking is needed on how the potential benchmarks might form a comprehensive benchmarking framework and what further benchmarks are needed. The other sections of this report, the analysis of the WP3 case study findings and outcomes of the CoP workshops, will also provide guidance on this to allow these issues to be taken forward in WP5 and particularly our final 'Gender Benchmarking Report' (D5.3).

3. BUILDING ON THE FLIARA WOMEN-LED INNOVATION CASE STUDIES

This section presents the results of a specific policy focused analysis of the FLIARA women-led innovation farm and rural innovation case studies (D3.3). This policy-focused assessment worked to understand the key barriers and opportunities facing women-led innovation in farming and rural areas of relevance for policy based on the case study findings.

Another important part of the FLIARA case studies and wider context to note is that the grounding criteria for selecting the innovative women to be interviewed for the case studies was that their innovations were inscribed in at least one of the four dimensions of sustainability (economic, cultural, social, environmental). As such, all data drawn into this report refers to and reflects the experiences of women who integrate sustainability into their innovative practices. Sustainability is the principle of addressing current needs and challenges while ensuring that future generations can meet their own needs. It entails harmonising environmental, social, cultural and economic factors to promote long-term well-being and safeguard natural resources (Farrell et al., 2023, p. 30, D1.1). Sustainability within the FLIARA context is understood to be an open concept which includes economic, environmental, social, cultural, and institutional dimensions. Institutional sustainability revolves around inclusive, flexible governance that empowers rural actors to influence decisions shaping their future and integrates their perspectives across all dimensions of sustainability. Gender equality within FLIARA is conceptualised as having three elements: recognition of women's knowledge, norms, and values; fair distribution of benefits and costs between women and men; and the opportunities for women to participate in decisions concerning their own lives. FLIARA examines how the three elements of gender equality are interlinked with dimensions of sustainability.

3.1 FARM INNOVATION CASE STUDIES: EMERGING FUTURE POLICY NEEDS AND PROMISING DEVELOPMENTS

A wide range of needs emerge from the FLIARA women-led farm innovation case studies suggesting improvements that merit policy attention relating to the innovation and enterprise support system. In the sections below, across a number of key areas, policy needs and gaps, but also promising developments are discussed. Tables throughout this section present ideas for 'targeted actions' that could be adapted as potential benchmarks. The tables are not intended to be exhaustive. They are an exercise in identifying potential actions to help inform what we benchmark and what indicators we use.

Better supporting women-led farm entrepreneurial innovation

Maximise digital and technological skills and opportunities

Women farm innovators showed considerable interest and capacities around applying digital and technological solutions in developing and supporting their innovation. Digitalisation also brings benefits such as increasing flexibility to balance work-life and open access to markets for more remote locations. Investment in rural broadband has opened better access to such tools. One common area of strength identified was using social media and more broadly having a web presence supporting marketing and sales, such as highlighted from the findings a range of case studies (e.g. Finland, Spain, Sweden, Netherlands, Italy, Ireland, Slovenia). Wider business and sales support can be gained by using online sales and ecommerce to connect directly with consumers as well as reach broader markets. These were aspects also more specifically discussed in the Spanish and Netherlands case study assessments. Social media is also useful for networking as well as empowerment of women where it can be used as a tool to share knowledge and information.

While women farm innovators are making use of digital applications and possess skills, there is still a strong case for providing additional training to further build on these already strong capacities. For example, from the assessment from Spain, the Netherlands, Italy and Ireland this applies to a range of areas, ensuring women are making the best use of business and innovation digital applications such as in marketing, online sales, accountancy and customer relationship management. While skills do appear well developed among the successful innovators studied, gaps and weaknesses may still exist outside of this group, as well as within it. Digitalisation is a fast-changing space. This is highlighted in the Czechia assessment which points to the fact that digital skills are understood to be lower in rural areas therefore making education important. Further to this, more newly emerging areas, such as artificial intelligence, are showing potentially wider gaps. The risks of digital technologies and artificial intelligence is another wider issue potentially needing attention to limit challenges.

Tailor supports to different stages of the innovation journey, particularly early stages

Generally, support for farm women innovators at key stages of their innovation journey emerged as a weakness in the current support system, based on the case study assessments. This is discussed specifically in relation to access to finance (see further discussion below), but is also a wider issue. In relation to early stages of the innovation journey, challenges at the start-up stage were a widespread issue among innovators interviewed in the Italian and Irish case studies. More specific issues were the lack of business start-up training opportunities tailored to different business stages as highlighted in Spain's case study assessment. The farm case study in Sweden identified that the youngest entrepreneur interviewed felt they needed to improve their business skills. The assessment in Sweden also suggests youth business training in schools as a promising support however a greater focus on running a business rather than starting up

is needed. This is also seen in the Irish case study assessment, while not specific to start-ups, it is found that specific issues such as dealing with tax and VAT become needed in the day-to-day operation of a business and require particular knowledge and skills. The Italian and Irish case studies point to the need for wider action outside of the education system with describing the potential need for a dedicated support programme or innovation incubators for start-up and early-stage women-led innovation. Networks emerged as a key factor supporting success in many case studies (as discussed further below) and a lack of networks is pointed to in Slovenia's and Sweden's case study as a constraint for early-stage innovators. Ireland's assessment also pointed to the importance of ease of access to information to develop key skills and connect to wider networks to allow the innovation's early-stage development. Peer-to-peer learning appears important, as pointed to in reflections emerging from the Irish and Czechia assessments. This would assist current successful women innovators support those aspiring to and starting innovations.

Access to networks and role of different kinds of networks

The case study assessments highlight and underline the importance of networks in successful women-led innovation. Innovators make use of different kinds of networks for different purposes. Women can engage in local, regional, national and European level networks, for example described in the German and Netherlands case study assessments. The importance of supporting networks is also illustrated in the Irish, Netherlands and Spanish assessments. For example, they are described to enable a range of benefits such as: knowledge sharing, problem solving, connecting with resources (including sharing of resources), collaboration across regions, building reputation, providing an advocacy platform and improving the visibility of women-led innovation.

Supporting networks is therefore a key part of facilitating women-led innovation. One particular area of need that emerged was the role of networks in relation to skills development, which is discussed further in the section below 'specialist skills and peer to peer learning networks'. The role of targeted networks for women innovators also emerged. For example, the Netherlands case study assessment outlines an idea for a new policy support that would facilitate the creation of dedicated spaces within agricultural networks for female innovators. Similarly, the Spanish assessment outlines an idea for a new policy initiative supporting professional networks for women farmers. This network could have specific functions and activities such as advocating for their needs as well as focusing on sharing knowledge and resources. A note of caution around networks solely for female innovators is highlighted from the Irish case study assessment. The potential for women-only knowledge transfer groups is provided for in Ireland's CAP 2023-2027. The Ireland farm innovation case study identified a scepticism related to these knowledge transfer groups because of the potential creation of silos. The value of men and women's engagements and joint networking is also raised. A key point appears to be the availability of a diverse range of networks so that women can become part of women-only networks if they feel they are valuable, but also that female innovators can become part of wider and diverse networks at different scales.

Specialist skills and peer to peer learning networks

In many of the case study assessments the importance of specialist skills is outlined because farm innovations are diverse. For example, the idea of life-long learning is alluded to in the wider suggestions emerging from the Irish case study assessment. Key issues highlighted are the continued availability and access to skills training, as well as ensuring this stays up to date and aligned with new knowledge and changing needs.

Barriers to accessing skills were also described. Spain’s case study assessment notes that geographical proximity to agricultural colleges could enable easier access to upskilling opportunities, hence those further away may be challenged to access this education. The Irish assessment notes that innovators often resorted to self-learning using internet resources to overcome immediate skills gaps, such as developing a website. Weaknesses in the availability of skills training in specific farm innovation areas (e.g. alternative agricultures such as organic, biodynamic, regenerative, permaculture) is highlighted in the Spanish and Italian case study assessments. More broadly, a general lack of availability of training in alternative agricultures through public institutions is highlighted in the Italian farm case study assessment.

The role of professional networks to gain more specialist skills is also noted in the Spanish case study assessment. Their enhanced support is outlined as an idea for improved policy supports. This also links to the concept of peer-to-peer learning. Connecting innovators in specific fields to share knowledge and learn appears a promising initiative to support knowledge exchange and transfer. Peer to peer learning is also pointed to in the Italian assessment in terms of playing a role in knowledge development and where weaknesses are identified in training related to alternative agricultures. More broadly, the Netherlands assessment outlines an idea for new policy around women-centered mentorship programs. Women in the Irish case study benefited from this type of a programme and ACORNS is presented as a potential promising practice. More broadly, practice-based learning can be important and the Czechia assessment also points to the potential in supporting demonstration farms.

Table 8: Innovation and enterprise support system: Ideas for potential benchmarks and examples from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
A dedicated support programme targeting start-up or early-stage women-led innovators exists that provides a range of supports, such as grants, mentoring and skills training	The Empowering Women in Agri-Food Programme run by the European Institute of Innovation and Technology and co-funded by European Union provides training on how to manage a farm-related business. It was a useful training support and contributed to network development for an Italian farm innovator.

<p>Innovation incubator type supports exist supporting start-up and early-stage innovation idea development and testing</p>	<p>The Italian case study assessment outlined an idea for a new policy support related to municipality run 'community labs' for food processing.</p>
<p>Initiatives support peer to peer learning in the farm innovation contexts</p>	<p>In the Irish case study the 'ACORNS programme' emerges as a potential promising practice that connects early-stage rural female entrepreneurs together and with 'lead entrepreneurs' to learn together and grow a business. The German assessment points to the Meisterbrief qualification as a promising policy measure that provides education preparing for running your own business or a high position at a company. Holding the Meister certification confers the special right to train apprentices. More broadly an idea for a new policy measure suggested in the Netherlands assessment was development of networking platforms at local and regional levels to connect female innovators with environmental mentors and collaborators to further leverage their sustainability commitment. More broadly too another idea presented in the Netherlands assessment is financial incentives for knowledge-sharing initiatives.</p>
<p>Specialist skills training initiatives support upskilling in areas relevant to farm innovation and needs of women in farming</p>	<p>In the Irish case study assessment, the example of 'Skillnets' is identified. This programme exists in Ireland to support upskilling in partnership with industry in specific economic sectors, for example one exists in organics. An idea to adapt this concept is discussed around developing a women-led farm innovation Skillnet that could address women's specific needs and skills issues.</p>

Improved access to a more diverse range of finance supports

A clearly universal issue was the need for improved access to finance. This is a crucial issue because it links to the ability of women-led farm innovations to start, grow and more widely survive. The need for a more diverse range of finance supports broadly emerged and some ideas for access to finance supports that could address challenges are outlined in Table 9.

Under-funding and private funding emerge as patterns. In the German assessment an example of a women innovator working without remuneration to start-up an innovation is outlined, but they could then secure funding at a later stage of development. The use of personal, private sources of finance, such as family loans and personal savings, is also evident in a number of the country case studies. This underlines a disadvantage for women without such sources of finance and the particular importance of public grants and loan finance availability to ensure a more level playing field to enable women-led innovation. A wider observation from the Spain and Ireland farm case studies was that non-traditional financing (e.g. crowdfunding, consumer pre-payments) were not commonly found and there is room to further assess the potential of these type of finance. Finland notes there is room for more support for experimenting with business ideas.

There is already specific economic support for start-ups and new enterprise in Finland, but this kind of support could still be expanded.

Access to finance impacts the type of innovations that are possible. For example, those that do not require large initial investment would be less inhibited than more technological innovations that need significant starting capital. For example, in the Irish assessment the ability of some women to run businesses 'on a shoestring' is identified, however the Slovenian assessment makes the point that technological innovations can require greater financial investment, meaning innovations are under-funded or cannot get started due to limited capital. Similarly, the Spanish case study assessment highlights women that based their innovation on family-owned farms could innovate in technology more readily.

Financial incentives are available and provide an important source of financial support. These were mostly non-targeted supports. Various sources such as national (e.g. Local Enterprise Office in Ireland, Swedish Agricultural Agency, subsidies for renewable energy in Spain, the Slovenia Enterprise Fund) and EU (e.g. LEADER, support through CAP interventions, such as young farmers supports) measures were highlighted as important. However, to better support the nature of women-led innovations they need to be more targeted. This was not necessarily an isolated issue specific to women-led innovation, but a range of wider issues relevant to particular types of farm innovation emerged:

- Innovations can be smaller scale and based on small farms calling for more targeted financial support for small scale businesses and farms.
- Innovations can be slow growing calling for finance supports that are perhaps phased and provide finance support at key stages of this slower pattern of growth across time.
- Innovations that focus on different forms of development, not solely economic but work towards creating social, cultural and environmental benefits calling for more targeted financial support for social, cultural and environmental innovation.
- Innovations in more alternative forms of agriculture, such as farms focused on special breeds, as well as regenerative, organic and biodynamic farming, calling for targeted agricultural financial supports more focused on alternative agricultures.

Improving finance that is available to non-profit organisations, run by volunteers, who provide important social or environmental services is also important. For example in Sweden, finance of this type is available but the amounts of funding are extremely low, compared to those available for profit oriented businesses.

Access to credit from banks was also a difficulty emerging facing women-led farm innovation. The Spanish assessment notes difficulties in securing bank finance for example because of financing requirements and gender biases not looking favourably on small scale, women-led projects. The Irish and Italian case study assessments also highlight female innovators reluctance to get into personal debt, because of the

uncertainty around future innovation economic success and personal risk if not able to re-pay loans.

Many assessments (e.g. Ireland, Italy, Spain) also pointed to the fact that existing sources of finance also come with bureaucratic barriers such as complex application processes, strict eligibility criteria, competition for funds and length of timescale between application and receipt of funds. The issue of a mismatch between the time investment, complexity of application and the actual funding amount was also raised in the Ireland and Sweden assessments.

Weakness also emerged in relation to access to finance tailored to specific stages of business development. It also appears to remain a challenge across the innovation journey and is an ongoing issue for women-led innovation beyond for example business start-up. For example, in the Slovenia assessment it is highlighted that in later stages of innovation development the need for investments related to areas such as technological modernisation and equipment purchase can still need to be supported by access to finance. Similarly, the Irish and Spanish case study findings highlight that innovations can have specific technical needs and investment is needed to enable this. An incremental pattern of innovation and business development was described based on the Swedish and Irish assessment of case studies. For example, project-based funding was highlighted in Sweden as not fitting with this growth pattern. The Irish assessment put forward an idea for new policy as finance supports designed to support incremental business growth rather than a focus on scale up and fast growth (e.g. business acceleration grants).

Table 9: Access to finance: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Finance support target women farmers	This could take different forms such as budgets within non-targeted finance supports are ring-fenced to support women-led innovation. This is highlighted as a new policy idea in the Spain and Ireland case study assessments.
Finance support target specific stages of innovation development	These could take the form of targeted grants tailored to support women-led innovation and specific stages of innovation development. This is highlighted as a new policy idea in the Italy, Spain, Slovenia and Ireland case study assessments. One more concrete example (yet not targeted to women) is identified in the Irish case study assessment. This was a competitive start-up scheme that aided late-stage start-up next steps.
Availability of a state-supported micro credit scheme	The Italian case study assessment outlines a new policy idea that is a micro credit scheme and it would provide quick and easy access to limited amounts of funding (e.g. €20,000-€40,000) that is available to start-up and later developing innovations. This idea was suggested by several of the interviewed farm women innovators.

Financial support programmes targeting new entrant women farmers	The Italian case study assessment outlines a new policy idea relating to a financial support scheme targeting women who did not inherit a farm, start their innovative project from scratch and engage in projects focusing on alternative agricultures.
Support for collaborative organisational forms and membership based organisational models that also facilitate pooling and sharing of financial resources	The Netherlands case study assessment outlines a promising practice, the Herenboeren cooperative, that provides a membership-based financial model. This allows members to pool financial resources. It reduces economic pressure on individual women farmers and helps improve economic stability. In Sweden there is a part government funded advisory organisation, Coompanion, targeting and supporting cooperative behaviour and organisations.
Grant support for farm modernisation and application of new technologies	In Ireland through the CAP 2023-2027 the Targeted Agriculture Modernisation Scheme supports investment in farm modernisation of buildings and equipment. This scheme also provides a higher grant rate to women farmers.

Improvements in policy and law to support access to land

Issues related to land access were common in a range of case studies. However, in Sweden availability of land did not emerge as an issue in the farm case study, which could merit further investigation.

Access to land is particularly difficult for women farm innovators who do not inherit land and therefore implies the need for a greater focus in policy. For example, in the Italian case studies the availability and cost of land is a barrier for most young people. In Ireland, the innovators in this case study found a route to entry into women-led farm innovation through the family farm or marrying a partner who was farming. The Netherlands and Slovenia case study assessments both point out that access to family land allows entry into women-led innovation without significant set-up costs. Spain's case study also highlights similarly that family farms can provide a key resource and infrastructural base for business establishment.

Slovenia also points out that access to land, through other means such as partnership or purchase, provides a solid base for starting women-led innovations. Uncertainty and insecure land access is also a core barrier related to access to land and women-led innovation. Leasing land provides an avenue to access land for farming. However, the availability of long-term leases presents a barrier for women-led farm innovation, as described in the German and Netherlands case study assessments. The cost of leasing land can also be an issue. The Italian case study assessment points to one example that facilitated overcoming this barrier where a favourable rental rate assisted one innovator access forested land owned by the local municipality and develop their innovation. These types of issues are also pointed to in the Spanish case study where the need for improved supports (e.g. laws and bureaucratic processes) to facilitate land lease and purchase, also specific to women-led projects, is needed. The dual issue of longer-term land access and projects that focus on farming for nature also emerged in the Netherlands policy assessment. It is noted policies that incentivise biodiversity actions

provide both financial and logistical support, but also that these projects can take a long time to mature. This means it is important that long-term political commitments supporting land tenure security in relation to particular sustainable farming practices is needed.

The German assessment points to the opportunities to access farmland following the end of the German Democratic Republic and sub-division of large collective farms to make land available for private ownership. Three women-led farm innovations featured in the case study benefited from this. While this represented particular historical circumstances it is noted this does underline how availability of land facilitates women-led farm innovation.

For women-led farm innovation cultural norms also inhibit land access for women who do have linkages to family farms. For example, while there are examples of women taking over farms even though they had male siblings, the German case study assessment still identified a gender bias towards sons in land inheritance is identified.

Potential important levers to improve access to land pointed to in the case study assessments and wider reflections are outlined below in Table 10. These include initiatives involving public land and more collaborative forms of farming.

Table 10: Access to land: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Initiatives are in place supporting public land access	The Italian case study assessment suggested a new policy idea around the establishment of public-private collaborations to support access to public land to assist women-led farm innovations develop. Another idea that also links to assisting testing of novel farm innovations for those without land is where local governments facilitated access to public lands or facilities, also sometimes supporting research on local varieties of crops. A few examples of this are found the Italian farm case study. The Netherlands case study assessment presents a new policy idea around expanding land leasing programs providing opportunities to access land via municipal and provincial support, making farming more accessible for women without needing to own land. Alongside this, the fact that some local municipalities and regional policies facilitate land leasing for eco-friendly farming is highlighted as similar opportunity.
Farm succession supports are not gender blind and address gender-specific cultural norms inhibiting farm succession	The German case study assessment highlighted the need for intermediaries supporting the opening of a dialogue on farm succession in the farming community, as well as showcasing examples of women successors.

Policy dialogues on access to land for farming (led by Government) are being run. They also focus specifically on gender issues and actions are being developed based on these dialogues	The German case study assessment suggested a new policy action idea around access to land support events that bring together practitioners, such as young farmer associations, and policy makers to discuss access to land issues such as focusing on succession and access to land for new entrants.
Supports exist to match land supply and demand	The German case study assessment suggested a new policy action idea around facilitating brokerages to match farmland supply and demand to support innovative farming practices, as also suggested by Padel et al. (2022) based on a national study on women in agriculture.
More favourable land lease conditions are provided for in law that supports access to farmland	The Netherlands case study assessment presents the land policy 'Didam arrest' as a promising policy measure that allows for tailor-made land lease leasing conditions to be set by municipalities linked to their wider policies. For example, this could aim to facilitate more alternative farming models (e.g. CSA), approaches (e.g. biological farming) and small-scale farming.
Law and policy facilitate more collaborative forms of farming	The Netherlands case study assessment presents a new policy idea around creating simplified legal frameworks for cooperatives that reduce administrative burden and cater specifically to women-led farms also helping reduce initial land investment. The Italian case study assessment suggests a new policy idea around the strengthening public-private collaborations such as establishing tenders that assign women farmers to manage a public plot of land and run a farm-based business on it (e.g. open a farm-based restaurant or kindergarten).

Challenges related to the wider regulatory, legal and support system

Barriers that discourage farm innovators from engaging with the existing support system were evident in the case studies. The bureaucracy attached to applying for funding and time needed to devote to completing applications emerged as a key issue from the case studies. The need to review, streamline and simplify processes to reduce bureaucracy was pointed to the Italian, Ireland, Czechia and Spain assessments as key issues. While policy measures did provide support, the attitude of German farm innovators was not to look towards supports to help start-up their innovation calling the effectiveness of existing supports into question. Improving availability of information then becomes important to ensure women are not missing out on available assistance. The Italian, Irish and German assessments also highlighted the need for better information on available supports and assistance with the process as key issues. The German assessment also specifically highlights how only one interviewee mentioned LEADER and there appears a need for better information on the support and opportunities provided by the LEADER programme as well as becoming involved in the governance of the programme. Italy also suggested

the need to set out rules stipulating deadlines and timelines for project evaluation and funding receipt. These types of issues were pointed to generally in many of the case study assessments but did not often highlight particular policies or programmes which may merit further examination within the case study evidence. Sweden did however distinguish that difficulties were experienced, namely with CAP applications, while LEADER appeared to be the exception. However, for example, in Ireland and the Netherlands LEADER emerged as a programme seen as bureaucratic and difficult to navigate for many women from a time perspective.

The slow nature and bureaucratic burden attached to regulatory and legal systems is also raised, such as in the Ireland, Slovenia, Italy and German assessments. Italy and Spain for example highlights how gaining permits to develop new farm services can be a barrier. Spain and Slovenia also cite obtaining leases for public land as another example. Planning permission for on farm buildings was highlighted as a challenging, complex time-consuming process in Ireland's farm innovation case study. The need for reassessment of some regulations also emerges as an issue. Finland for example notes the example of producers that follow organic principles but still do not meet regulated standards and cannot receive certification. The stringency, and potential over-stringency, of food production hygiene standards is highlighted as a barrier to farm businesses in the Czechia assessment.

The Czechia assessment also notes how there is criticism of taking the approach to favour women for support when starting an agricultural activity. Finland discusses how Nordic equality policy does not allow positive discrimination, while it is argued that affirmative actions can sometimes still be called for to support gender equality. There is what might be referred to as a 'Nordic gender neutrality ideal' aspired towards. It seems depending on where and how affirmative action measures are implemented this could have different effects and be more accepted. For example, in Ireland's farm case study scepticism was raised in relation to women only knowledge transfer groups provided for in Ireland's CAP CSP because of the potential creation of silos, the potential for segregation of women instead of bringing them into the core of farming better and also the value of men and women's engagements and joint networking.

A wider issue in relation to national gender equality policy is also pointed to in the Netherlands assessment. The Netherlands' national emancipation policy (emancipatienota) does not specifically address the needs of rural women. More broadly too the need for place-based policies or policies that respond to local needs and challenges also emerged. For example, Slovenia points to remote areas as facing specific challenges for women-led farm innovation particularly linked to long distances. Ireland's case study also identifies place-related issues. It is outlined how location also presented different types of farm business opportunity for women-led farm innovation. Some rural farms can more easily link to neighbouring towns or wider regions depending on distance and communications infrastructure.

Table 11: Support system: Idea for potential benchmark and examples from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Public grants and wider support and regulatory system includes intermediaries supporting information provision on supports as well as navigating the application processes	Italy’s farm assessment suggests a new policy idea where there is a ‘hub’ type (e.g. website plus in person support) facility that links female innovators to information on supports, but also staff that can support applications linked to different funding programmes. Ireland’s farm innovation assessment describes a similar idea where intermediary level supports exist, with for example support staff in-between funders and applicants that can guide and assist the funding application process.

Important role of women-led innovation in renewal of the farm economy

Increasing multifunctionality

Policies that tap into and support the multifunctional role of farming appear important to harness the role of women-led innovation in renewal of the farm economy. For example, the Czechia assessment highlights that opportunities can be created for women when the multifunctional nature of farming is promoted. The space occupied by women-led innovations in agriculture tended to be less conventional forms of farming practice, from certified organic farming to more broadly biodiverse, regenerative and sustainable farming practices using approaches such as permaculture or biodynamics for example. Women are motivated by addressing sustainability in its different dimensions, particularly environmental cultural and social. The scale of farms and farm businesses is also a pattern identified in how women-led innovation can play this role. For example, the need for a stronger focus on supporting smaller scale more resilient farm businesses is pointed to in Sweden’s assessment. Further to this the nature of Sweden’s innovation system can mean more technological larger scale innovations are more suited to support. The need for a more fundamental reorientation of the support system to ensure there is room for supporting smaller, more resilient business is noted. Ireland and Slovenia’s assessments make similar points in relation to the struggles of the small farm. Slovenia’s assessment highlights a key challenge in the interviews was that small farms struggle to complete in regions where the farm economy is dominated by large scale operations. Ireland’s policy assessment of the farm case study reveals that farm innovators aim to enhance the viability of their farms and ensure their sustainability for future generations. However, they do not seek to create large-scale businesses with high turnover. Instead they aim to focus on developing businesses that complement the existing family farm and align with its scale.

More specifically a greater policy focus on farm diversification could further enhance the role of women-led innovation in farm economy renewal. One avenue highlighted as an opportunity was in relation to supporting short food supply chains, which was specifically pointed to in the Italy and Czechia assessments. Extending the focus in policy beyond the farm gate and better harnessing opportunities for shortening food supply chains

between farmer and consumer, as well as developing more direct connections between them appear important. Further to this another aspect of farm diversification that emerges as an opportunity links farming into other aspects and needs of the rural economy, such as social farming, green care, farm-based childcare services, environmental education and heritage-based projects, were described in different ways in the Finland, Italy, Czechia, Ireland and Netherlands assessments. Czechia's assessment also pointed to the opportunity to better embrace more novel trends such as technological advances and digitalisation in specific areas such as precision farming

Changing perceptions of farming and who is a farmer and innovator

Part of how women-led innovation feeds into renewal of the farm economy is by helping to change the narrative. There does appear to be room for a more proactive focus on this through policy measures. For example, the Czechia assessment points to the fact that agriculture has a poor image and women can play a role in changing this, presenting it as an attractive profession that is essential to food security and landscape maintenance. Women leading innovations want to change the narrative around rural areas and farming and focus their attention on it. A feeling of attachment and loyalty to the farm and wider rural area can also exist. For example, this is specifically identified in Ireland's and Italy's farm case studies. The path into farm innovation can be a colourful one and have an interesting story embedded within it. Farming and innovation may be a path not taken at the start of a career. Women can enter farming after spending time in urban areas and non-farming careers, as pointed to in Spain's assessment. If latent demand to enter or return to farming exists, policy measures could be designed to tap into this, as well as showcase these stories to change what are perhaps narrow ideas on who and what a 'farmer' is.

Many case studies also point to how women leading innovation use the media, in particular social media to promote their work. More broadly also for example the German assessment points to a strong desire among the farm innovators to tell stories about food and farming. Ireland's case study assessment points to how the case study identified an important role for the media in highlighting and raising awareness, recognising and celebrating women-led innovation and changing perceptions around cultural norms and gender roles.

Table 12: Supporting renewal of the farm economy and women-led innovation: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Increase farm women's capacity to change perceptions of farming	The German case study assessment suggested a new policy action idea around including marketing, media and PR skills in the curriculum of coaching programs, as well as more broadly supporting more media work for women farmers through cultural grants. Similarly, the Irish case study assessment suggests an idea for new policy measures supporting collaboration among creative sectors (e.g. TV, radio, artists, craftspeople) and women-led farm business to not alone increase awareness of existing women-led innovation but also benefit both sectors through developing collaborative projects harnessing synergies.
Better leverage existing women-led farm innovation to change perceptions of farming	The Netherlands case study assessment suggests a role for the promotion of female role models. The Spanish case study assessment suggested a new policy action idea to promote knowledge exchange and transfer of experience between women in farming who enter into it from different sectors, also to increase visibility of such women as a means of inspiration.
Strengthen supports for farm diversification	The Irish and German case study assessment pointed to the need for greater support for farm diversification. In the Irish case it is suggested the need for development of a dedicated farm diversification support programme that has a targeted focus on women-led innovation. The German assessment identifies an innovative funding instrument implemented in Baden-Württemberg through the LEADER program that targets partners and female family members of farm owners and provides coaching and subsidies for farm diversification. The Netherlands case study assessment pointed to the need to revise restrictive land-use regulations to accommodate multifunctional farms and initiatives involving for example eco-tourism, social farming, and education.
Strengthen supports for the development of short food supply chains	The Italian case study assessment suggested a new policy action idea around enhanced spaces and possibilities for producer and consumer connections, such as making spaces for public markets available.
Directly target and incentivise women's return or entry into farming	The Irish case study assessment suggest an idea for a 'return to farming' innovation grant to support women that have left to return would help to further harness this opportunity for women that have not yet returned but hold a desire to.
Strengthen supports for more ecological types of farming	The Romanian case study assessment describes a new policy idea around strengthening financial incentives for agroecological practice programs and biodiversity conservation at the farm level.

Need to directly tackle traditional gender norms and gender specific barriers in farming

The persistence of traditional gender norms and gender biases in farming and farm business contexts is clear from the farm case study policy assessments. This raises the need for policy measures that tackle attitudes and raise awareness of successful women-led innovation. A series of potential actions are outlined in Table 13. For example, Sweden's farm case study assessment points to how farm innovators meet prejudices as business owners, such as feeling they are not taken seriously as entrepreneurs. Italy's farm case study assessment outlines how patriarchal attitudes persist in farming, again with women not being taken seriously in this male dominated field. Italy also highlights that challenges can also exist within the family as they may not support a woman successor becoming a farm manager. Finland's farm case study assessment identifies that female farm innovators can have to work at proving themselves and older males can particularly have old-fashioned attitudes relating to gender roles. Spain and Ireland's assessment also highlights similar struggles relating to being taken seriously. For example, Ireland's farm assessment describes how local attitudes to women farmers include not being considered a 'serious' farmer and just farming as hobby. Germany's farm case study assessment also raises the issue of more subtle and unconscious gender bias also as an issue. The Netherlands assessment highlights how female farm innovators can face scepticism and judgment in remote areas. Issues related to traditional agricultural vocational training programs are also raised in terms of how they can lack female inclusivity which contributes to reinforcing the high proportion of males in farming.

Farm machinery and clothing also emerge as an issue, discussed particularly in the Italian and Netherlands farm case study assessments. The assessments identify that machinery and clothes are designed and more suited to male builds and users. Italy highlights a need to advocate for female-calibrated machineries and farm clothes. The Netherlands suggests the need for policy measures encouraging manufacturers to consider gender in agricultural technology design as well as training programs tailored to women's needs.

The need for women's improved involvement in decision-making spaces in farming and impacting it also emerges from the case studies. The Czechia assessment points to the general low representation of farmers in politics in general, which includes a low representation of women. Female farm innovators may also need support themselves to ensure they have capacities to become involved in decision making spaces. The farm innovators in the German case study did not see themselves as having a role in influencing policies or regulations. Spain suggests that strengthening networks among women farmers could help to play a role in this helping to provide a space where their voice can come together and find a place in policy discussions. The Netherlands assessment finds that women innovators can face isolation in leadership roles because of gender biases which in turn can inhibit their recognition and impact.

Table 13: Tackling gender norms and gender related barriers: Ideas for potential benchmarks from the case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Tackle traditional gender norms related to farming through actions targeting girls and boys	Italy's assessment highlights the need for a focus on girls to consider agriculture as a career, such as promotional campaigns focused on the opportunities that multifunctional agriculture offers and also through making women already in agriculture more visible. Ireland's assessment highlights the potential room for measures that target secondary or third level education sectors promoting opportunities for women in farming and success stories to encourage women in farming careers.
Increase the profile of successful women-led farm innovation in local farming communities	This could be done through events at the local or regional level where women farm innovators can showcase their work to demonstrate the value of their innovations to local people, as suggested in the Italian farm case study assessment. The Netherlands assessment suggests a potential role for local and regional government sponsored public awareness programs and community-based gender-awareness programs.
Build knowledge and capacities of staff of key local and regional institutions in farm-related gender equality issues	Italy's assessment highlights the need for training of local public officers, LAG members and other farm-related organisations about gender equality and the value of women-led farm innovation.
Measures are in place to assist improved gender balance in agricultural training programmes	The Netherlands assessment highlights the need for reform of agricultural curricula to emphasise inclusivity, also with a greater emphasis on developing soft skills such as communication and marketing.

Social, personal, work-life and rural service issues

The number of clear 'targeted actions' emerging from this section is low. The general discussion does however reiterate the importance of some of the targeted actions identified in existing policies in Section 2 (e.g. see Table 7). A tentative but noteworthy observation is that some areas may be difficult to address with traditional policy measures, suggesting the need for more innovative approaches in this space.

In the farm innovation context, the support of partners and family (immediate and extended), as well as wider social connections such as friends and community is a key support identified in many case study assessments. The social capital that family and community networks provide generates different types of support, from helping with

childcare to providing financial support. This raises a question in relation to women's capacity for farm innovation when they experience social exclusion and deprivation. The case study assessment in Sweden raised this directly questioning what system supports these women, also pointing to the fact that their innovation capacity is unlikely to be realised.

Spain's case study assessment makes the point that work-life issues such as childcare and domestic commitments must be considered key issues in the context of farm innovation. Different women experience different barriers. The point is also made that business supports on their own will not address the barriers faced by women involved or aspiring to be involved in farm innovation. For example, for women with young children, the case studies showed that access to childcare and after-school care can be a barrier. Further relating to this issue, differences among the countries is identified and Sweden appears at a distinct advantage. However other countries highlight issues, such as Italy where childcare access appears more critical. The Italian case study assessment highlights being both a mother and farm manager as a barrier with the need for improvements in availability of childcare and after-school care. Italy also discusses how farms can become part of the solution through the development of farm-based kindergartens.

Family leave allowances were also discussed in different ways. The need for improvements in maternity leave allowances for self-employed women and farm managers is also highlighted in the Italian context. The Czechia assessment notes that while women and men can share parental leave, the vast majority is taken by women. The Czechia assessment also notes that besides parental leave allowance, other avenues to assist combining caring responsibilities and employment should be considered such as shared roles and more secure pre-school care.

Mobility issues can also be a barrier. The length of time it takes to travel to access services, such as schools and childcare can create added time pressure to already stretched demands meaning potentially remote rural innovators are at greater disadvantage, as well as countries such as Finland where with low population density means long distances are inevitable. In many countries, lack of public transport is highlighted as an issue. The Czechia assessment argues that it is important optimal public transport systems are created which cannot done commercially meaning use of local and regional budgets is essential. Road infrastructure in remote rural Italian areas is observed to impact mobility in different ways. For example, Italian farm innovators can be isolated from services such as childcare, but also it creates challenges for viable businesses that attract visitors, such as Agri-tourism. Sweden's assessment highlights the transport of people and goods as issues, such as time taken and unreliability around delivery of goods.

Improving how women view themselves as farm innovators is also an emerging issue. Women's feeling of 'imposter syndrome', lacking confidence and a sense of belonging in the space of farm innovation was identified for example as part of Ireland's farm

innovation case study assessment. Creating a more supportive environment, such as enhancing mentoring and networking opportunities could help address this.

Table 14: Addressing work-life issues: Ideas for potential benchmarks from the case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Focus on childcare provision that meets the needs and opportunities of the farming profession	The Italian assessment pointed to the need to adopt new rules allowing farm managers to hire education professionals needed for farm-based kindergartens. The Netherlands assessment points to a further, more tailored need around childcare availability and the role of developing more flexible childcare support to accommodate rural farming schedules.
Ensure there are adequate parental leave allowances for self-employed women and farm managers	This emerged broadly in the case study evidence and specific examples are illustrated in Table 7 above.

3.2 RURAL INNOVATION CASE STUDIES: EMERGING FUTURE POLICY NEEDS AND PROMISING DEVELOPMENTS

Similar to the FLIARA women-led farm innovation case studies, a wide range of needs emerge from the farm innovation case studies suggesting improvements that merit policy attention. The sections below follow a very similar format to section 3.1 above where across a number of key areas, policy needs and gaps, but also promising developments are discussed. Also throughout this section tables present ideas for ‘targeted actions’.

Better supporting women-led rural entrepreneurial innovation

Maximise digital and technological skills and opportunities

The need for specialised training in digital and technological skills is also highlighted in the rural case studies. For example, Spain points to a lack of technical skills in rural areas limiting adoption and use of new technology, alongside the need for specialised funding supporting women-led innovation to apply digital technology. Digital marketing skills are identified as a gap in Finland’s rural innovation case study and the importance of this skill for business promotion is pointed to in the Italian context. Finland’s assessment also points to the fact that this can also be a time-consuming activity which also presents a barrier, suggesting direct support for digital sales and marketing could also be supportive. Romania identifies a lack of digital education as a broad barrier to rural women-led innovation. Recent greater policy attention to digital transformation is also highlighted in Romania, such as through the Recovery and Resilience Plan where funding supports a range of measures such as upskilling programs to improve digital competencies, including actions like transforming libraries into digital skill hubs to train citizens from disadvantaged communities in digital literacy and entrepreneurship. However, the issue of EU policy not always aligning with local needs, along with limited scale of the measures implemented, is also highlighted. The availability of advanced technological equipment and high costs of access, such as for facilitating product development, is highlighted as a barrier in the Netherlands assessment. More broadly reducing gender biases in technical sectors is also highlighted as a barrier in the Netherlands assessment.

Better enable innovative rural business start-up and development

While improving access to finance emerges as a critical issue (discussed further in the section below) in the rural innovation case studies, tackling this barrier alone will not provide a supportive enabling environment for women-led innovation. Finland’s rural innovation case study findings clearly demonstrate this point. It is reported that the process of starting a business in Finland is not complex and municipalities provide a range of supports. Evidence from Romania shows a different story in relation to starting a business pointing to a lack of adequate entrepreneurship legislation, excessive bureaucracy and an often-changing tax system, which can push women-led rural innovation into a space within the informal economy.

Finland's rural innovation case study findings suggest finance is not always what is most needed. It is suggested that support for rural entrepreneurial innovation needs to take a more integrated approach and target different stages of innovation development with a diverse range of measures (e.g. access to finance, business training, digital marketing, supports targeting experimenting with novel ideas). Ireland's rural innovation case study shows how women-led innovation can develop in an organic way, rather than for example following a business plan highlighting the need for supports that allow a business to expand slowly, be led by and adapt to their own development and opportunities that arise. Further to this, it emerges that supporting rural innovation, including women-led, needs to look beyond STEM and high growth fields and ensure the support system does not exclude small innovative rural enterprises. This is a point emerging from the rural innovation case studies in Sweden and the Netherlands. However, this does not mean there is not a role for STEM. For example, the Netherlands also points to the opportunities by taking a more tailored and targeted focus on STEM in rural areas. The Netherlands also suggests an idea for new policy that could introduce STEM-focused programmes targeting rural women, but with an emphasis on technology for sustainable innovation.

Focusing on different motivations for rural innovation can also shape available supports and mobilise untapped opportunities. For example, the German case study identifies the trend being a 'lateral' entrant to innovation where there is a career transition and entering into innovation without formal training, also suggesting that this potential could be directly tapped into and supported. Motivations can also link to a desire to live in a rural area, as identified in Finland's assessment that points to how entrepreneurship can enable women living in the rural North to stay there and make a living. Policy measures could also be designed to enable these types of patterns.

Knowledge, skills and peer to peer learning

The need for entrepreneurial and business skills is evident as a need from the rural innovation case studies. The evidence points to the importance of such training, as well as a network-based peer to peer approach to learning. Slovenia and Romania also suggests this type of training and general awareness raising of opportunities could also be more focused, such as in areas such as social and environmental entrepreneurship, as well as targeting training at different levels such as in schools. Other skills are also needed of course, but these can be specialist skills to the particular area of innovation and case studies demonstrate how women acquire these skills in different ways, sometimes formally, others informally. Ireland's case study assessment suggests a potential need for support of soft skills, such as leadership skills to help deal with imposter syndrome or matching experienced and starting innovators to provide lived experience and peer to peer support.

Access to networks

Places and spaces where women can network are key to facilitating rural women-led innovation, therefore supporting networks and networking emerges as centrally

important to facilitating women-led rural innovation. Networks provide many benefits, such as connecting women to potential collaborators, information and as a wider source of support. Ireland’s assessment points to how networks and peer support provide a core and crucial role to support innovators (access to information, emotional support, confidence building, build business trust and reputation). Also finding like-minded people to network with and learn from was important. In the context of gender-related barriers, networks can also be important. For example, the Italian assessment points to how in the presence of patriarchal social norms networks provide a space for women to connect on common challenges such as this. Romania points to supporting the development of mentorship and networking platforms tailored to rural women innovators as a new policy idea. Being able to develop a large and diverse local, national and even international network also emerges as important because different networks can provide access to different kinds of benefits. For example, Finland’s assessment points to the importance of non-local, external networks to learning and innovation to ensure external influences and ideas influence innovation practice when relevant. Formally organised networks, such as through the CoP model, are suggested as a potential lever in this space. Digital networks could also facilitate these type of networking engagements, as well as others. The Netherlands assessment for example suggests that digital platforms can assist women-led projects gain visibility, connect with urban markets, and attract broader support. Ireland’s assessment points to how networking can be a challenging activity to engage in because of the time commitment needed suggesting an idea for new policy measures related to providing financial incentives to participate in networks to compensate for more direct work time lost.

Table 15 below draws together some ideas for targeted actions emerging in relation to the above sections and the broader area of better supporting women-led rural entrepreneurial innovation.

Table 15: Better supporting women-led entrepreneurial innovation: Ideas for potential benchmarks and examples from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Digital and technological skills and capacities are built across and within rural communities particularly targeting women and girls	The Romanian assessment suggests new policy ideas linked to a number of different levels of action, such as improving the curricula and teaching of the mandatory Information and Communications Technology subject in schools as well as free access to technological equipment in villages and communes. In the Netherlands the role of shared technological resources, such as through regional innovation hubs offering technical support and free access technical equipment allowing for experimentation with ideas is discussed as a promising, replicable model for other regions. Support for local governments to host hackathons or idea-sharing events focused on rural challenges is also discussed by the Netherlands.

Financial support for rural entrepreneurial innovation targets different sizes of business, particularly small rural businesses	Finland's assessment points to the need for smaller, more flexible funding options for small businesses and if not a full-time entrepreneur. Supporting part-time entrepreneurs is suggested as an important aspect to assist stepping up to full-time entrepreneurship.
Incentives support local production	Finland's assessment suggests a potential role for tax reliefs for businesses that make their products domestically and encourage local production and further employment.
Rural innovation supports target non-traditional fields of innovation and more locally embedded and sustainable entrepreneurial innovations	For example, Sweden's assessment points to a potential new policy idea where the innovation system supports initiatives designed to decrease consumption. More specially, Romania's assessment identifies the local gastronomic point law (412/2023) as important to facilitate small-scale, family-based food businesses in rural areas to while preserving cultural heritage.
Community-led rural development funding has an enhanced budget for rural entrepreneurial innovation	Many rural innovation case studies reference the LEADER programme as an important support that promotes community-led local development.
Widespread public availability of business and entrepreneurship training	Italy's assessment points to the need for more systematic and ongoing widespread regional availability of courses on entrepreneurship.
Supports directly and formally facilitate peer to peer learning	The Netherlands assessment highlights how peer learning could also focus on wider goals that present potential innovation opportunities, like the intergenerational transmission of skills, such as traditional farming methods and ecological knowledge. Formal mentoring and peer learning networks for women innovators in this area could support such processes.
Supports target rural return migration and entrepreneurship with a focus on encouraging women return migrants	The Romania assessment suggests a new policy idea where national-level scholarship programs specifically target rural women and there are re-entry programs for women to return and apply their skills in rural contexts, including grants for start-ups or innovative projects upon their return.

Need for improved access to finance

The need for improved access to finance again appeared as a critical issue to support women-led rural innovation, both to start-up and establish innovations, but also grow and develop them further. Similar to the farm innovation case studies, women leading rural innovations do tap into existing sources of financial support and can make use of a wide

range of sources of finance. They also can try to navigate ways around limited access to finance such as using private donations, and pointed to in Romania, or personal savings as emerged in the Irish case.

The issue of more targeted finance supports towards the specific needs of rural innovative and women-led business emerged. Spain's rural innovation case study identified this issue and pointed to some specific needs around the need for microloans, grants for specific types of businesses and funding pools dedicated to sustainable rural innovations. The Italian and Romanian rural innovation case study also identified the need for micro-credit. Italy also identified the issue that there can be a need for existing capital alongside grant support was pointed to as an issue in the Italian assessment. Without access to a source of match funding, rural innovators cannot make use of particular grants. Similar to the farm innovation case studies, the Spanish and Irish case study assessments also pointed to the potential for further exploration of non-traditional funding sources. Romania pointed to some examples of how women have leveraged practices such as bartering and gift economies to bridge resource gaps, showing possibilities in this area. The issue of not wanting scale-up innovations also emerged in some cases. For example, Finland points to an ethos of 'do what you love and stay small' emerging from the rural innovation case study.

The need for improved access to finance for specific rural innovation sectors as well as stages of innovation development also emerged. The need for improved access to finance for particular sectors within the rural economy was also pointed to in some assessments. For example, the social economy emerged in the Slovenian context, Romania pointed to the need for better subsidy access for ecological, cultural, or social innovation and the Netherlands technological innovation. The Netherlands pointed to the need for improved start-up financial support. The Ireland assessment identified that access to finance needs can differ at different stages of business development (e.g. idea development, start-up, scale-up). In the case of some rural innovators, start-up costs were manageable, but finance needs became greater to facilitate business development after the initial start-up phase.

The cost of employees emerged as a particular issue in some of the rural innovation case studies. Voluntary and family labour can be used in some cases to overcome this, as highlighted in the Finnish and Italian rural innovation case studies. Generally also rising costs, such as gas and electricity, were highlighted by the Finnish rural innovation case study as a financial challenge. Italy identified that they could create jobs, but the cost of employment can be too high for small women-led rural business. Italy suggested a need for simplifying and reducing costs for small rural women-led businesses, such as by providing exemptions from contributions for the first years in business. In Germany an example a federal employment scheme incentivized the hiring and retraining of long term unemployed is identified (see Table 16). Taking on employees is important to facilitate business development and if it is prohibitive potentially stagnates the business. For example, in Finland women-leading innovations could benefit from employees, but hiring employees was too financially risky. They needed to develop to a stage to start to make profits, otherwise they needed to shut down. Overcoming the financial risks with

employment could potentially facilitate the next step needed to help build a more resilient development pattern.

Similar to the farm innovation case studies, access to credit from banks was also a difficulty emerging facing women-led rural innovators. In Spain it is observed that the design of local products did not fit small-scale or start-up rural businesses because of high interest rates or unfavourable repayment terms. The existence of as well as in relation to gender-biased stereotypes was also identified as barrier. In Ireland rural innovators did not often access to finance through banks was not common. Pre-conceptions about the attitudes of banks existed impacting women even considering approaching the bank for finance. Those with prior business connections and engagement with banks appeared to have a more positive attitude and confidence to approach banks for finance and therefore felt there was an ‘open door’.

Table 16: Access to finance for women-led rural innovation: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Financial support programmes target rural women innovators	In Finland the availability of loan support for female entrepreneurs through Finnvera was a government support introduced during Covid.
Availability of a state-supported micro credit scheme for rural business	Also pointed to in the farm innovation context, the Italian rural case study assessment outlines a new policy idea suggesting a micro credit scheme providing quick and easy access to limited amounts of funding (e.g. €20,000 - €40,000) for start-up and later developing innovations.
Measures support reduced wage costs for hiring employees in start-up or micro/small rural innovative businesses	In Germany an example is identified where one innovator benefited from a federal employment scheme that incentivised the hiring and retraining of long-term unemployed people through wage support. This system is also in place in Sweden. The assessment from Sweden also points to the need for support systems to account for voluntary work, and perhaps fund it to a greater extent, also highlighting that to continue long term, as well as support growth and development of the innovation this calls for some form of payment.
Incentives exist to support starting an innovative rural business	In Italy the programme ‘Resto al sud - Remaining in the South’ supports the establishment and development of new entrepreneurial and freelance activities in the South of Italy.
Explore the untapped potential in more alternative economic approaches	The case study assessment from Romania identifies potential in solidarity and social economy practices and suggests a new policy idea around introducing legal and institutional frameworks that formalize and support this approach such as tax benefits to businesses and organisations adopting solidarity practices.

Issues relating to the regulatory and support process

Regulatory and support system

Similar issues as highlighted in the farm innovation context around bureaucratic barriers discouraging innovators from engaging with the existing support system were also evident in the rural innovation case studies. Many of the rural innovation case studies highlight how there is a valuable support system in place, but bureaucratic barriers are implicated in potentially limiting its impact. Repeated issues in the rural innovation context were the bureaucratic and time-consuming funding application processes as well as the need to review processes to reduce bureaucracy and simplify processes. The LEADER programme again emerged as an example of an effective support, but also that reform needs to address the associated bureaucracy and improve its impact, for example as highlighted in the Netherlands assessment. These issues can contribute to discouraging women leading rural innovations from benefiting from supports, as pointed to in the Spain and Netherlands assessments. This therefore may hinder mushrooming innovations that do not then succeed in gaining supports. Sweden points to how the language used in the support system can be technical and need for example business training to assist understanding the requirements. The need for better information on supports available and assistance with the process was also reiterated in many of the rural case study assessments.

Wider insights also emerged on the nature of the support system and more innovative types of policies that appear needed to better support women-led rural innovation. The need for targeted measures and affirmative action does appear in the case study evidence, alongside for example a place-based approach. Ireland's rural case study assessment suggests there is a need for targeted support to address specific needs and challenges faced by rural businesses and women leading innovations in these contexts. More integrated policies also appear a promising approach. For example, concluding reflections from the Netherlands assessment suggest policies that combine rural development, environmental sustainability, and gender equality goals, at both local and national levels, are called for. It is also suggested by the Netherlands assessment that greater flexibility in planning frameworks would provide a further assistive system, such as when it comes to spatial planning regulations impacting the development of innovative rural projects supporting sustainability. Place-based policies are also pointed to as a promising approach.

The bureaucratic burden and challenges created by regulatory and legal systems was also reiterated in the rural innovation context. Further emerging issues here were the cost of complying with regulations for small rural women-led innovations. Sweden points to the fact that for rural innovators to achieve compliance this needs resources creating difficulties for start-up innovators particularly. Regulations can also limit economic opportunities in other ways. For example, they can restrict development of innovative activities, such as the issues related to selling peasant seed varieties as highlighted in the Romanian rural innovation case study assessment. Seed production at this scale can

experience difficulties complying with EU and national seed laws that can require seeds for sale to be registered in the EU seed catalogue.

Table 17: Support system: Idea for potential benchmark and examples from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Public grants and wider support and regulatory system includes intermediaries supporting information provision on supports as well as navigating application processes	This could be actioned in different ways. One existing measure found in Sweden was how some municipalities had an innovation advisor who acts as an intermediary between the national support system and rural entrepreneurs. Sweden also describes in its rural innovation case study a new idea to support start-ups where a user-friendly web-based system could provide information on everything they should consider, as well links to assistance organisations. Similarly, Romania suggests a potential role for support centres so that rural women entrepreneurs can access information, funding, and legal assistance.

Important role of women-led innovation in renewal of the rural economy

Increase rural multifunctionality and unlock rural resources in new ways

Similar to the farm case studies, an emotional attachment to rural areas is identified among the rural innovation case study evidence, alongside a desire to contribute to rural revitalisation. Improving rural sustainability is a strong motivator. Women can identify untapped value in a variety of ways in their rural environment. The Netherlands and Ireland case study assessments points to women leading rural innovation as important rural change agents. This can be for example local cultural and artistic heritage, as the Italian case study highlights. Ireland and Finland assessments suggest a key motivator is also a desire to live in a rural area. Finland points to an example of how one innovators business is inherently based around what will work in her locality and the place she wants to live. Opportunities embedded in the rural environment are clearly outlined in the case study assessments from Spain and Finland. For example, the rural innovations in Finland show examples of being connected and tapping into the innovation opportunity and value in local culture and nature. Innovations and rural economy developed in this manner based around harnessing local resources can also have the benefit of enhancing local autonomy, as pointed out in Romania’s assessment. Projects can have a revitalising role and rural innovators are often embedded and active in their rural communities. For example, this is pointed to in the German assessment how projects have added to the social life in rural places proving new meeting places. Both the German and Romanian case study assessment point out how women-led innovation can help address local needs, such as targeting marginalised groups or victims of domestic violence, through

their innovations. Social enterprise emerges as an area of opportunity case study assessment from Spain and better support for solidarity-based economies in Romania. They can bring new ideas to rural areas, such as in one German case applying digital technology to improve their eco-tourism enterprise. Spain also identifies how technological opportunities are harnessed such as renewable energy technological solutions and agricultural technologies to enhance soil health. More broadly Spain pointed to how the case study demonstrates how technology is a significant enabler to address barriers and can help to streamline operations, reduce labour and overcome geographical barriers. Environmental innovation is also an area of opportunity. Slovenia and the Netherlands for example point to an opportunity linked to promoting circular economy business and innovation concepts.

Changing perceptions

Women leading farm innovation can battle against traditional, conservative views and stereotypes. This is pointed to different ways in the case studies. For example, Italy identifies strong patriarchal social norms in rural areas, potentially stronger in remote rural areas, as well as a mistrust of women that are rural newcomers and establish their innovations in a rural place. Germany points to the fact that improving gender equality can be an impact and motivation for the rural innovators. Slovenia also identifies how their can be negative attitudes in the local environment hindering cooperation, for example because of a lack of familiarity or negativity towards certain non-traditional activities, such as complementary medicine. Sweden points to the fact the female newcomers in rural areas helped to contribute to shifting more traditional norms, pointing to a potential role for rural newcomers in changing traditional norms and stereotypes

Similar to the farm case studies, media attention helps rural innovators to gain visibility for their business, but also counter stereotypes and change the narrative on rural business and innovation, such as more traditional gender stereotypes on rural jobs and opportunities. Italy for example highlights how media assist business promotion and potentially inspire other women to develop similar projects. Romania points to how visibility campaigns and local markets have provided platforms for rural women to showcase their products and innovations.

Table 18: Supporting renewal of the rural economy and women-led innovation: Ideas for potential benchmarks from case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Strengthen supports for rural economy under-exploited rural opportunities	This could be assisted in a variety of ways to better support areas such as social, cultural and ecological innovation. An idea that links to this from the Romanian assessment is to develop regional hubs for testing and marketing rural products. The Italy assessment suggests a policy idea could be to financially support and allocate resources for women-led rural cultural and artistic initiatives. Romania suggests there is a need to establish long-term funding for rural cultural initiatives. This could also focus on tapping into

	place-based opportunities (e.g. rural-urban connections) as they can differ depending on the type of rural area. The Netherlands assessment also highlights the need for locally-led approaches where local governments could play a more pivotal role in aligning women-led innovations with broader sustainability goals and highlighting the need for more localised support mechanisms. Community-led approaches are also signalled as important for example the Romanian assessment points to an idea for new policy linked to community-led ecotourism projects in protected areas that promote biodiversity conservation and local economic growth.
Develop legal frameworks and support systems that facilitate community ownership or use of rural assets	The Romanian assessment points to an idea for new policy linked to laws that support rural community ownership of rural assets such as forests and pastureland. The Netherlands highlights the need for municipalities to recognise women-led projects that have been transformative in rural land management supporting various aspect of sustainability (e.g. transforming barns into cultural hubs). It is suggested this could include creating land grants or affordable leasing options as well as encourage partnerships with local authorities to co-develop and manage community land.
Strengthen supports for exploiting technological and digital opportunities in rural innovation	Spain's assessment points to an idea for new policy to increase grant support for women-led business to cover general technological supports and access lower cost infrastructure and tools. In the German assessment eco-tourism is given as an example where, support services, either centrally or peer-to-peer, could tap into the use of technology to establish innovations in this area. The Romania assessment also suggests that women have particular capacities and interests in sustainable technology, which suggests this could also be an important area of focus.
Increase rural women's capacity to change perceptions of the rural economy	Spain's assessment points to the need for increased training related to utilising digital platforms, online marketing and social media for business promotion. A similar idea is pointed to in the farm section (Table 12).
Better leverage existing women-led rural innovation to change perceptions of the rural economy	Increasing the profile of existing women led innovation could be done in different ways. A similar idea is pointed to in the farm section (Table 12). The German assessment suggests a new policy idea around giving greater recognition by extending of award programs. The Romanian assessment suggests a new policy idea could be to develop a nationwide marketing campaign highlighting women's rural businesses, backed by public and private partnerships. The Netherlands assessment also points to the potential need to target particular areas, such as women's role on safeguarding cultural and landscape heritage.

Need to directly tackle traditional gender norms and gender specific barriers in rural areas

Similar to the farm innovation case studies, the persistence of traditional gender norms and gender biases in rural innovation contexts is seen in the case study policy

assessments. This again raises the need for policy measures that tackle attitudes and raise awareness of successful women-led rural innovation. A series of potential actions are outlined in Table 19.

The need for and value of women's improved involvement in decision-making spaces is also clear from the rural innovation case studies. Case studies describe positive effects of women in decision making and leadership positions, such as seen in the Spanish and Romanian contexts. For example, Romania points to the fact that the simple greater presence of women in elected positions can help to open doors for more women and contribute influencing women's empowerment, helping counteract gender stereotypes and contribute to building trust. Italy for example outlines the opportunity in supporting women's better participation in public institutions such as at local municipality level to ensure their needs are advocated for and improved support gained. Supports that build capacity and skills to engage in decision making directly appear important and are identified in case studies. Romania also points to the need for more role models to inspire other women. The issue of gender stereotypes and traditional views on gender roles are also highlighted as creating barriers to women's participation in decision-making and leadership roles more broadly. Romania for example points to these deeper societal issues.

More broadly traditional gender roles and norms are identified as persistent issues impacting rural women-led innovation, albeit with some changes and improvements. Romania and Spain for example point to persistent traditional gender roles associating women with motherhood and domesticity. The Netherlands assessment points to how persistent traditional gender roles and patriarchal values can contribute to undermining women's credibility as innovators in rural areas. Linked to this, Finland for example points to how rural innovators need to actively work harder to prove themselves and traditional gender roles and stereotypes are part of what leads to this issue. Maintaining and building confidence can also be challenging for women innovators in the face of these issues. Sweden's assessment also identifies that rural women innovators feel they do work harder to prove themselves, particularly in more traditionally male dominated rural sectors. The assessment from Czechia draws the broad and important conclusion that women need to feel supported by both society and men.

Table 19: Tackling gender norms and gender related barriers in rural areas: Ideas for potential benchmarks from the case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Increase the profile of successful women-led rural innovation	Spain's assessment suggests ideas for new policy measures to increase recognition and awareness which could take the form of a range of actions such as workshops, training sessions, and educational programmes.
Increase education around gender equality	Romania's assessment suggests that education for gender equality should be part of the mandatory education curricula, also with adaptations in different contexts (e.g. focusing on local context issues). More broadly the Netherlands assessment suggests a need for national campaigns to challenge gender stereotypes and women's contribution to rural innovation.
Supports exist that directly focus on supporting women's better participation in decision making	Different ways of tackling this emerge from the case studies. The German case study assessment identifies a state funded coaching programme supporting women entering local politics and points to its relevance in other places and potential transferability. Romania suggests targeting actions towards political parties where for example policy conditions tie public funding to gender diversity and training programs. Proposals also exist in Romania to introduce gender quotas in local and parliamentary elections. The Netherlands also points to the importance of quotas in local government contexts and where there are quotas for women in leadership or community this is helpful.

Social, personal, work-life and rural service issues

Improve self-perceptions

As also highlighted in the farm innovation section, improving self-confidence and how rural innovators perceive themselves is a challenge facing women-led rural innovation. Finland's assessment highlights the low proportion of female to male entrepreneurs generally in the country. One idea for new policy noted is the need construct programmes to improve self-perceptions of aspiring women entrepreneurs. Ireland's assessment highlights how life-stage appeared important to possessing the confidence to initiate a rural innovation. This seemed not to come readily when young but when more life experience was gained. Interviewees ranged from mid 30s to over 50s and some commented on how they had gained the confidence to take a chance to try and fulfil an

ambition at this life stage. Similarly, Finland's assessment highlights that individual professional challenges (e.g. dissatisfaction with previous employments) and life stage (e.g. having children) was a catalyst for rural innovation. This suggests the need to identify age-related barriers to rural women-led innovation, but also a potential to tap into ambition for women-led innovation in mid-life stages.

Family, home and rural living

Similar to the farm innovation context, social capital and the support of partners and family helps to facilitate women-led rural innovation. Family provided important support such as sharing childcare and being a source of motivation and reassurance. For example, Spain's rural innovation case study highlights the role of family in helping innovators address scepticism within the local community. Benefits were not just being broadly supportive of the innovation but also extended into a wide range of areas. Family resources helped overcome the need for finance, such as using a family-owned premises to develop the business, as highlighted in the Italian rural innovation case study assessment. In the German assessment an example is cited where family were an important source of technical know-how. Finland's assessment suggests family could also assist with connecting the innovator into key networks in some cases. Moving beyond the realm of family Finland's assessment points to a sense of community and helping each other as an opportunity that facilitated women-led rural innovation.

Also similar to the farm innovation context, female rural innovators with children mention services that facilitate balancing of business and family commitments. Perhaps an extended list emerged in this context, but this does not mean they are not still issues for female farm innovators as work-life balance is strained in almost all national assessments. The Italian and Germany case study assessments for example point to ideas for new policy to include improve provision of services such as childcare services, schools, school buses. Italy also adds this is particularly important in remote rural areas. The rural innovation case study assessment from Sweden identifies access to pre-schools and schools as essential and that rural innovators with children would not live or start a business in a place without these services.

Discussion of parental leave is also reiterated in the rural innovation context. The German assessment points to the need for good parental leave conditions in supporting work-life balance. The rural case study assessment from Sweden notes that being parent did not present an obstacle to rural innovation, but the Sweden's welfare system appears crucial to this exception with its paid and shared parental leave and public childcare supports. It is noted that this system has changed patriarchal norms where men take parental leave too.

The issue of women taking on a greater burden of domestic and childcare responsibilities also re-emerged in the rural innovation case studies. Finland's case study policy assessment identifies the need to challenge the unequal childcare burden women face, also because rural female innovators can risk burn-out. Ireland rural innovation case study assessment also notes that rural innovators found it challenging to balance

domestic, caring and business tasks. There was a tendency to put family first which perhaps could however place a limit or slow business development. Spain's case study assessment notes that rural innovators in these circumstances can adapt which leads to their innovations being of a nature that accommodates flexible working arrangements and home-based work. The potential for innovations possible through home-based work is also impacted by the availability and quality internet access (discussed further below). The Romanian case study assessment similarly also notes that these issues limit many rural women's possibility to engage in innovation, but also more broadly engage in public decision-making and initiatives outside the home. The Czechia rural innovation assessment makes a similar point. An interesting policy initiative was identified in the German assessment. The German federal government is currently implementing on 'caring masculinities' to work towards more gender equality in this area. The point is also made in the German assessment that gender equality policy needs to include a focus on, and continue to focus on, boys and men. The Romanian case study assessment points to the need for education for gender equality as a new policy idea.

Similar to the farm innovation context, family and community networks can provide important support. However, all women may not have these networks. For example, Finland's assessment points to how single mothers and those without family support networks childcare services become even more essential to enable them to capitalise on a desire to become involved in rural innovation and entrepreneurship. Ireland's assessment also notes that depending on the women's personal situation, the need for different services arose and barriers arising due to deficits.

Improving maternity allowances for women entrepreneurs is reiterated in the Italian rural innovation context. The German assessment identifies a pivotal example of where a self-employed carpenter downsized her business and dismissed employees because of childcare challenges. This innovator was then motivated and driven to lobby for and successfully campaign for adequate maternity leave support for self-employed.

The challenges of living in a rural area due to rural service deficits also emerge in the rural innovation assessments, such as mobility issues related to public transport and accessing nearby healthcare. For example, basic services, such as schools, shops and post offices were highlighted as leading to depopulation and were highlighted by Italian rural innovators. Finland for example also points to the fact that young and educated women tend to leave rural communities creating demographic imbalance. The Romanian case study assessment points to the need for prioritisation of women's needs in rural services and infrastructure planning. Ireland's rural innovation case study assessment also makes the broad policy-related observation that rural services is a long-standing policy challenge but clearly needs addressing not only to support rural communities but also rural business development. The Czechia assessment points to the importance of making regional cities and rural settlements well connected by public transport. The integrated transport system in the South Moravian Region is cited as an example that provides at least eight connections to each inhabited place on weekdays and three connections on weekends. It is also noted however that integrated transport systems can

lack immediate economic feasibility and be unprofitable, but addresses other losses created by a lack of transport connections.

Broadband access

Technology opens many avenues benefiting rural innovation, such as efficiency improvements, online marketing and sales channels. Quality, reliable broadband is key to ensure access. Sweden’s rural innovation assessment finds that all rural innovators had broadband access, and it was essential. Ireland’s rural innovation case study identifies improvements in rural broadband in recent years, with improvements particularly seen for those located close to urban areas. The National Broadband Plan is the core policy and its continuing roll out is highlighted as crucial. Similarly, the Netherlands rural innovation case study identifies that investments in broadband access have been a critical enabling factor for rural innovators to expand their digital footprint and market reach. Spain points to the lack of access to advanced technology and digital infrastructure as major limiting factor to the potential for innovation in rural areas. Romania identifies both internet access and remote working options as opportunities that can help provide women with economic stability by enabling entrepreneurial activities, but also that rural internet services lack penetration in some rural areas.

Table 20: Addressing rural services and work-life issues: Ideas for potential benchmarks from the case study assessments

Targeted action	Examples
Integrated approach to rural development policy taken that deals with gender equality issues in the domain of work and life	This point is argued in the German assessment suggesting an integrated policy approach covering rural development, labour and family policy is needed and policy improvements in this area could make being self-employed, work and living in rural areas more attractive. The case study assessment from Ireland argues there is a need to recognise, embrace and support the distinctiveness of women-led innovation rather than shaping it in a generic mould. That means supporting, facilitating and encouraging the combination of family and business life
Better harness digitalisation and the potential for remote work, innovation and entrepreneurship	Romania’s assessment outlines a new policy idea around providing tax benefits or incentives for businesses employing remote-working rural women or support for digital nomad initiatives tailored to rural women.
Provide paid parental leave that is shared between parents	Sweden’s welfare system provides for 480 days of paid, shared parental leave and good access to public, affordable childcare

3.3 CASE STUDY CONCLUSIONS: A WISH LIST OF FUTURE POLICY NEEDS?

Taking the lens of working to identify policy needs from the rural and farm innovation case studies has been a fruitful exercise. The findings here will also inform WP5 of FLIARA. In an effort to condense the wide range of issues highlighted in this section, the range of areas that need policy improvement have been condensed into a 'Wish list' of aspirational policy objectives. This is also an exercise to assist with identifying key issues to be brought forward to the next CoP Policy Design and Assessment workshops.

Table 21: Aspirational policy wishes emerging from the women-led farm and rural innovation case studies

Area of need for policy improvement	Policy 'Wish'
Maximise digital and technological skills and opportunities to support women-led innovation	Training in digital and technological skills development is easily accessed and improved funding is available for female farm and rural innovators to support use of new technology and digital applications.
Tailored innovation supports are available to better support different stages of the farm and rural innovation journey	A range of supports are available (e.g. access to networks, training, mentoring, finance, innovation incubators, business and enterprise skills development) tailored to emerging, start-up, early stage and maturing women-led farm and rural innovations. In the farm innovation context this also includes focus on the issue of access to land. Measures are needed tackling different parts of this issue, such as directly accessing land (e.g. land matching, public land leases) and tackling cultural and social succession barriers (e.g. intermediaries support farm succession conversations and planning).
Improvements in networking opportunities, particularly those that facilitate peer to peer learning to develop specialist skills	Farm innovators are enabled to participate in a diverse range of networks through the existence of measures to ensure diverse networks exist (e.g. funding for stakeholder organisations, networking events organized by public bodies). Networks also have a focus on facilitating peer to peer learning to help practice based knowledge exchange and development of specialist skills.
Improve access to a more diverse range of more targeted finance supports	A more diverse range of finance supports (e.g. grants, low-cost loans, micro-credit, tax incentives) are available supporting women-led rural and farm innovation. These supports also have innovative design targeting the needs of different scales of farm and rural innovation (e.g. based on small or micro farms and businesses) and types of growth patterns (e.g. phased support supporting slower growth).
Reduce bureaucracy in the regulatory, legal and support	Simplifications and flexibility measures are adopted in the support, regulatory and legal system where possible to better enable innovation and entrepreneurship. Assistance is

system. Facilitate women innovators to engage with the support system	available through intermediaries to help with applying for supports and information hubs exist on innovation and entrepreneurship supports.
The multi-functional role of farming and potential in the rural economy is better supported in policy frameworks	The support system targets areas such as social, cultural, digital and environmental innovation. There are more policies that are integrated across different domains. Place-based and community-led policy approaches are found more commonly used.
Measures work to change gender norms and stereotypes inhibiting gender equality in rural and farm innovation	Diverse measures work to impact change, such as promotional campaigns, education initiatives and capacity building training. Specific farm and rural innovation issues are targeted directly, such as career-based stereotypes including for example the need to tackle perceptions of farming and who is a farmer.
Improve rural services (e.g. public transport, childcare, broadband) and leave supports that women in farm and rural innovation can benefit from	Affordable rural public transport and childcare is available that meets the needs of the local population. Affordable, quality and reliable broadband is available in all types of rural places. Rural and farm innovators are supported to take leave in specific life circumstances (e.g. parenthood) and to ensure adequate work life balance (e.g. holiday leave).

4. FOCUS GROUPS ON POLICY BENCHMARKING AND POLICY DESIGN

This section complements the data presented in the previous sections based on the FLIARA Policy Assessment (D1.3) and Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking (D1.5), and case studies on Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas (Sivini et al. 2024, D3.3). Retrieving data through focus groups aimed to (1) verify the information collected in T1.4 and T3.3 in relation to the public policy and legal framework impacting rural women innovators, and (2) collect stakeholders' assessments of and experiences with the current policy and legal framework, by looking into its implementation and impact (Weir et al., 2024, p.46, D4.1).

Another very important objective of organising the focus groups within T4.3 was to facilitate direct dialogue among innovative women and a variety of stakeholders – including policy and decision-makers at national and EU level. These direct exchanges taking place during the CoP focus groups helped to identify where there are contrasting perceptions and experiences. However, we found that there is a significant overlap in what concerns the understanding of current challenges rural innovative women are facing. Engaging rural innovative women (and the rest of the stakeholders present) in discussions about the policies and legal frameworks that they navigated during the innovation journeys facilitated the identification of best practice examples. These examples can inform benchmarking efforts and provide a basic understanding of the contexts in which these were developed and implemented.

The focus group was designed to allow all participating stakeholders to engage in a guided discussion pursuing the above aims. The questions did not frame the policy measures – the discussants had freedom to bring into the conversation and address all and any relevant policy sectors and laws. This means that all the data collected, and the frequency certain topics were mentioned (such as for example the LEADER programme being mentioned at all tables during both focus group iterations) also indicate their reach/relevance/impact on rural women's innovation journey. The same holds true for policies which were not mentioned: some of the policies we had in the inventory from D1.3, or that had been mentioned in interviews conducted in T3.3 were not discussed as the participants did not bring them up. This means that they either did not have a relevant impact on the participants' innovation journeys, or they chose to prioritise other more relevant policies to discuss during for the focus group. Since the participation from all 10 countries was not homogeneous (with practitioners from the host country being overrepresented), the Irish and Slovenian national frameworks were more frequently discussed than the rest of national contexts.

The analysis of the data collected via focus groups, together with information from previous deliverables, as well as consultations among the authors of this deliverable led to identifying main topics, which are addressed below. While the questions of the focus group directly referred the innovation of women in rural areas, the discussions ranged

from specific national programs aimed at supporting women innovators (TAMS in Ireland, for example), to crosscutting topics such as the need for educational systems reform throughout the EU to advance gender equality. The discussion of these topics is organized to reflect current promising public frameworks and targeted actions identified, critical aspects, as well as policy suggestions extracted directly from the discussions, with potential benchmarks being proposed.

4.1 EXISTING SUPPORT FOR RURAL AND AGRICULTURE WOMEN-LED INNOVATION: PROMISING DEVELOPMENTS AND FUTURE NEEDS

Women in agriculture

Work in agriculture for women is one of the main crosscutting topics. The participants in the focus group highlighted the unequal work recognition in agriculture for women and men. This shows that, while gender equality is reflected to some extent in public policy regarding agriculture, there is still a lack of adequate prioritisation of gender equality across all sectors of public policy.

During the focus group, the idea that women employ more sustainable agriculture practices came up. This was doubled by the perception that these sustainable agricultural practices are not recognised as such, nor sufficiently targeted and supported by public policy and law. This lack of recognition of sustainable agriculture practices leads to the criteria for funding initiatives not being coherent with an approach which challenges current economic disparities from an intersectional perspective. The current agricultural system is unsustainable economically, favoring those who already have disproportionate access to capital.

This leads to an incompatibility of the current systemic constraints of industrial farming, including underpaying farmers, with them being represented in decision-making related to agriculture due to lack of time and skills. This means that the system does not take into consideration nor address farmers' needs, including those for basic social services and rural infrastructure. In turn, policies become too broad and not place based, with rural areas and people left behind in public policies. In part, this was attributed to a negative perception of agriculture as an economic sector at national level, and rural living more generally, found in various countries included in the project, including Ireland and Romania. As one of the women innovators shared about her experiences as a farmer in Ireland directly experiencing this:

“At times, in my opinion, we don’t have pride of place in rural Ireland, it’s a troubled love. I’m called the redneck in my family. The dynamic is changing, the respect level is changing.” (Practitioner, IE)

The role that farming organisations play within agriculture-related decision-making, and particularly women’s farming networks, was also touched during the focus groups. The need to get more women involved was noticed, as well as incremental improvement in both women empowering themselves, as well as in creating the conditions for them to

be better represented. Farming organisations seem to have more and more women’s networks included, as well have women in their leadership positions.

Immediate solutions identified during the focus groups were mentorship and support networks for rural women, including finance mentors, innovation incubators, and standardized programs, as crucial for empowering women entrepreneurs, farmers, and rural businesses to overcome skill gaps and scale successfully. This discussion is complemented by tackling the topic of women’s entrepreneurship and access to finance in the following paragraphs.

Table 22: Potential benchmarks for assessing public policies regarding women innovating sustainably in agriculture

Targeted action	Examples
Local, National and EU policies recognise and support ecologically sustainable agricultural practices and innovations	In collaboration with the Institute for Sustainable Development, the Organic School Garden Association in Slovenia manages the School Garden project - a network of over 100 school gardens was established in educational institutions of all levels throughout Slovenia, established in 2010. The work of the network has been recognised by policymakers at the national level and organic school gardens have been included in the Slovenian Action Plan for the Development of Organic Farming until 2027. Part of EU funded project EATHINK2015, the Association contributed to the scaling out of the model as best practice to other EU countries (Rural Factsheet #063, D3.3).

The LEADER Programme as a backbone support fostering innovation and sustainable development

The LEADER Programme was frequently named at both focus groups, in Ireland and Slovenia, as a critical source of support for rural women aiming to innovate as it is source of funding and support for local projects in various fields, including agriculture. It was referred to as an “important backbone” for concomitantly driving sustainable development and fostering innovation. This is particularly noted by respondents from Sweden (SE), Ireland (IE), and others, including researchers and practitioners. LEADER is valued by the women innovators for effectively combining sustainability goals with innovation, providing a support and funding platform where both can thrive and reinforce each other. Local Action Groups (LAGs) under the LEADER programme are noted for offering essential help and support to women in rural areas, providing resources and connections that empower women in these communities (noted in Slovenia, particularly by LAG participants, verified by data collected in Romania within WP3). What the innovative women would like to see more of is “LAGs work[ing] everywhere to give information to women about funding opportunities available” (Activist, IE).

However, some respondents, especially those from Slovenia, mentioned that access to LEADER support and funding is not always equitable. They cite excessive competitiveness, limited visibility and accessibility of some LAGs and suggest that program improvements are needed to make support more accessible and fairer. The LEADER Program could also significantly benefit from a reduction of the excessive bureaucracy and administration work involved, particularly regarding reporting requirements, which are burdensome and time-consuming for the women needing the support (to the point of deterring them from applying). Funding for LEADER initiatives is reportedly reduced, making it challenging to adequately support innovative projects and programs. This sentiment is echoed by respondents in Ireland (IE) and Slovenia (SL), especially among practitioners (women innovators) and LAG members. Additionally, adapting funding criteria to be more flexible and inclusive, accommodating diverse practical contexts and minimizing fund returns is seen as necessary.

EU Level

The Rural Pact portal was given as a positive example of information regarding EU funding available online. More than simply funding opportunities, EU support, education and funding programs (including LEADER and ERASMUS), international collaboration opportunities were highlighted by the participants in the focus groups and excellent occasions to network and forge durable partnerships and professional connections. This is even more relevant for the women innovating in rural areas, as their physical isolation (in part due to lack of infrastructure and reduced accessibility) prompts them to need both funding, information and support when implementing their projects.

Similar to feedback received about women's rural entrepreneurship, lack of information about existing funding opportunities, and a need for networking for good practices exchange indicate the pathway for improvement also in terms of funding.

Digitalisation

Digitalisation appeared during both focus groups as a significant opportunity for innovative rural women, as well as a challenge. Digital literacy for both rural women and men, and especially the elderly, is seen as an obstacle due to the limited access to training. Coupled with access difficulties to broadband, this can hinder significantly rural population.

However, the availability of digital technology, and especially digital connectivity and networking are also essential tools for women innovators. They employ these means to establish women's networks, communicate and organize. Also, they frequently use digital technology to access information, training and funding opportunities.

4.2 CHALLENGES RELATED TO RURAL SERVICES AND SOCIETAL TRENDS

Insufficient social services and public infrastructure continue to be issues the rural population must face in most of the 10 countries, which in turn disproportionately affect rural women. Among those which were indicated to have the highest negative impact are broadband, services, facilities, and infrastructure.

The lack of care services for children and the elderly, and particularly the unavailability of homes for seniors in rural areas, poses significant challenges in Czech Republic but not only. However, one positive aspect was mentioned at national level regarding various countries (Czech Republic, Sweden, Romania) was the possibility of long paid parental, and particularly maternity leave. Having the possibility of taking a long-paid maternity leave, and if there are also reinsertion incentives, greatly supports women in their innovative projects. Coupled with strong institutional childcare, for example in Slovenia, this leads to empowering of women to actively engage in women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas. This is a public policy practice that should be scaled to all EU countries, particularly given also the general trend of population ageing and also rural depopulation.

The topic of public transportation appeared as transversal during the focus groups as a challenge for rural women innovators. There is a great need to develop accessible transportation in order to overcome physical isolation, have access to more services, and be able to develop an innovative practice. One immediate but limited solution, as exemplified by Czech participants and applied in Romania (as per case study), is to have free public-school busses to facilitate the access of children and youth to education institutions.

Possibly due to a lack of valuing or rural living, the tendency noticed during the focus groups at national level is generally to disinvest in social services and public infrastructure in rural areas, the problem being that the lack of infrastructure in rural areas is isolating for the communities, hindering the economy and in general are not seen as a human rights issue.

Table 23: Potential benchmarks for assessing public policies regarding mobility in rural areas

Targeted action	Examples
Accessible public transport exists supporting the mobility of rural populations	<p>In both Czech Republic and Romania, regional (county) administration fund and arrange free public transport for pupils enrolled in school (school buses). This is particularly relevant given that schools in rural areas are being closed, and for women as much of their time is invested in care for children.</p> <p>Local community organizations engage in dialogue with local administration to find solutions for the introduction, extension or modernization of public transport (Factsheet #51, D3.3). Public transport is considered a community service of public utility, with relevant social and economic in terms of connectivity, inclusion and access to opportunities. Additionally, if administration opts for sustainable means of transportation (using regenerable energy sources), this also has an impact in reducing pollution (air and noise).</p>

Rural Women’s Entrepreneurship

Women’s entrepreneurship is one of the main areas that would greatly benefit from improvement in public policy and legislation, particularly at the national level, across the 10 countries and according to input from all types of participants in the focus groups. Employment laws need to be easier to navigate for small businesses, especially when it comes to offering benefits like maternity and parental leave. Similarly, the case of initiatives focused on production, the burden and lack of adequacy of workers’ safety regulations also hinder new businesses. An inadequate legal and tax framework, for example in terms of social enterprises (in Ireland), or artisans in Italy, restricts their possibilities to establish the kind of businesses they would like, in some cases pushing women entrepreneurs to operate informally to be minimally sustainable economically:

“There seems to be no one (no accountant, advisor, etc.) able to explain to you how things work, give advice on which tax number to open, etc. No one seems able to actually help if you want to open your own business as an artisan”
(Practitioner, IT)

Access to relevant information, adequate entrepreneurship training and mentoring programs for new women entrepreneurs is another crucial need across the 10 countries. This is seen as an urgent need, since the complexity of understanding the legal framework, managing paperwork for funding while simultaneously managing a farm or business is often unsustainable for rural women entrepreneurs:

“As an entrepreneur we don’t have time to research where to go.” (Practitioner, SE)

“It is very hard to start a business and then have to be a specialist in so many fields.” (LAG, SE)

A two-fold pragmatical solution was highlighted by various types of stakeholders from all countries participating in the focus group to respond to this need. Firstly, the long-term solution of including entrepreneurship in the standard education curricula. This should be complemented by accessible and women-targeted adult education learning opportunities in entrepreneurship to close the gap for the current adult generations. One possibility to enhance this solution would be to offer mentorship programs for women who wish to engage in rural innovative entrepreneurship.

Secondly, access to comprehensive relevant information about support opportunities and programs, public policy and legal frameworks, financing solutions should be provided in the form of one-stop-shops, such as for example national digital portals hosting this type of resources and making them available for free. Additionally, this repository of information could be used not just for public access, but also as a tool by the rural development consultants, entrepreneurship support services and all other relevant entities whose role is to support and encourage women engaging in rural innovation and entrepreneurship. Alternatively, another policy wish expressed during the focus groups, was that events to pair innovators with funding resources (public or private) should be organized and disseminated accordingly.

The broader economic landscape also works against women entrepreneurs, as large businesses often outcompete small ones, and women feel they need to resist the pressure to adopt male-dominated business practices (such as competition for higher profit, continuous growth). There is also a reluctance to use public funds to support small rural businesses due to the high failure rates - this points to a general lack of understanding that rural enterprises can contribute to both the economy, social cohesion and sustainability. Consequently, from a policy-making perspective, businesses not following a growth model but rather favoring degrowth, being community oriented and aiming for social impact rather than profit – such as social enterprises – are not seen as viable. What follows is that there is a major gap between public policy and lawmakers and how rural women innovators wish to run their businesses.

Different types of participants indicated that there is a lack of a coherent, holistic approach to supporting small businesses in rural areas, with inconsistent public policies creating additional burdens for women entrepreneurs (these policies also include access to basic infrastructure and social services in rural areas, as we will see below). Furthermore, the existing service providers often overlap in their offerings for new or existing entrepreneurs, and there is a need to refine their responsibilities to avoid confusion and improve accessibility, a situation particularly highlighted by participants from Ireland. Generally, rural women innovators and rural communities would benefit from targeted, coherent sectorial policies aimed at rural development through

entrepreneurship which understand entrepreneurship holistically – that is in its economic, social, ecological and cultural dimension.

One of the Irish women innovators shared that she successfully launched her food manufacturing business by leveraging tailored support at different stages of innovation. She began with a three-month online business course and progressed through local mentorship and health and safety programs. LEADER funding played a pivotal role in providing rural development support, enabling her to expand her capabilities. She enhanced her expertise by traveling abroad to master product development. At national level, the program offering education for food producers provided by Bord Bia (Irish Food Board, a semi-state agency working for small producers by promoting and certifying farmers' markets) which is a very important support now. This journey highlights how initiatives like LEADER, combined with mentorship and other national support policies, are invaluable for women practitioners in rural development and entrepreneurship as they can offer adapted support of different types, from different sources, adapted for the different stages of innovation.

Funding for innovations

Adding to the difficulties in terms of education for entrepreneurship and support systems is also the challenge of finding information about and accessing public funding, primarily at national level, but also at EU level. Many women indicated they lack knowledge of the policies and funding programs available, especially at supranational levels, making it hard to get started – this points to a need of the EU to improve its communication and outreach services, but also for national service providers to collect and make the information available. The already mentioned national repository of information and resources for entrepreneurs could be a solution for both.

“There is an issue around how to fund women. How to have targeted policies and with this being seen as gender discrimination?” (National Public Authority Representative, NL)

Several grants were mentioned that exist at national level and are useful for women innovators. Some examples covering different types of funding were: green loan schemes in Ireland, the startup grant in Finland and Sweden, Local Enterprise Office Business Expansion Grant for manufacturing in Ireland and Primo insediamento (First Settlement for women who want to start a farm business in Italy). While not all are targeted directly at women, in some cases, as it is in Ireland under TAMS (Targeted Agriculture Modernisation Scheme), women get a higher grant rate (women 60% and men 40% in TAMS). Other funding sources targeted at women which were mentioned as being helpful were ACORNS (Accelerating the Creation of Rural Nascent Start-ups) that aims at supporting early-stage female entrepreneurs living in rural Ireland and running over six months part-time. The Imprenditoria femminile programme was also mentioned which is a yearly program for women entrepreneurs, but not just in rural Italy. In Ireland, other funding directed at training provided important opportunities for women working in various sectors to expand their knowledge by gaining access to online

platforms such as Skillnet, or the BIA Innovation (food incubation and innovation campus supporting ambitious food businesses).

However, improvements are needed in terms of both distribution of funds, and funds return criteria: the criteria need to be adapted to the practical context of the beneficiaries and thus have wider criteria that encompass more diversity of situations. Restrictive conditions for applicants, together with not enough information and trained service providers, as well as infrastructure make access to funding difficult. What women participating in the focus group expressed as a need was diversified and simplified funding programs, which provide longer support.

There are additional aspects here related to funding policy design which require structural change in order to be improved. One of the needs highlighted is for attention to gender in general in development programmes, which goes hand in hand with the lack of prioritization of gender equality when designing funding programmes. In turn, this goes together with a need for gradual shift in mentality related to gender, which could happen thanks to EU educational and exchange programs. To complement this approach, the change in policy design and implementation would need to be accompanied by a gendered assessment of the policy impact.

Table 24: Potential benchmarks for assessing public policies regarding access to information about relevant funding and entrepreneurship opportunities for women

Targeted action	Examples
Accessible local and/or digital services exist which provide all relevant information and services to women entrepreneurs or who wish to become entrepreneurs	Local Enterprise Office - LEO (IE): "1st stop model" in each local authority area providing information and support on launching a business. Among the services offered are mentoring, training, food sector support, financial support, events. Programs ran by LEO, such as the "Business Expansion Grant", were considered by various participants in the focus group as having a social aspect, being age inclusive, supporting social enterprises and helping local economy. Local Advisory Offices (SI): provide information and services for entrepreneurs in rural areas

Common Agricultural Policy and CAP Strategic Plans

The CAP and the national CAP Strategic Plans were only seldomly brought up by participants in the focus groups, in both Ireland and Slovenia, indicating that for the innovative women and stakeholders present it was not a central policy. Positive aspects of the CAP and CSP mentioned were support for young and new farmers. Additionally, local advisory services in rural areas, such as those in Slovenia, were indicated to provide valuable assistance to farmers, and particularly women. In Ireland, the CAP provisions include female discussion groups, fostering community and knowledge-sharing among women in agriculture. However, excessive bureaucracy often deters

women from seeking support through the CSP. The funding criteria within CAP tends to favor large agricultural businesses, sidelining smaller farms, which are more common for women innovators. Additionally, conflicts between CAP policies and environmental regulations obstruct pathways to sustainable development which innovative women would like to engage on. Furthermore, the complexity of application processes and the need for advanced project-writing skills create barriers for women in accessing funding through CSP.

Cross-cutting and wider structural issues

During the data analysis, we have found that several topics were touched upon by the participants that relate to wider, structural or paradigmatic issues. They included the need for greater female involvement in farming organizations at both EU and national level, the role of grassroots networks in supporting women, and the influence of mindset and structural barriers on gender equality. There was a call for education to shift these perspectives, alongside advocacy for systems and policies that prioritize women's needs in agriculture and rural development so as to reach de facto gender equality.

Access to Information, Training and Education

Access to information, training opportunities for rural women and overall, a reform of the education system appear as crosscutting topics. As such, according to the participants in the focus groups, the education system across the EU requires significant renewal to better align with contemporary needs, including by integrating entrepreneurship and gender equality into the national curricula. Additionally, there is a notable lack of formal and informal education in areas such as finance, project writing, technology, and digital literacy, particularly for rural populations and the elderly, highlighting the need for targeted training programs to bridge these gaps particularly for women innovators. However, this also highlights the potential of entrepreneurship and gender equality education if included in educational curricula – this is seen as one of the few ways to advance structural change by all types of participants in the focus groups.

Additionally, access to information was also named as an important opportunity at EU level, in that knowledge exchange of best policy practices to tackle common problems at national, regional and local level could be employed. Direct political contact at this level, as well as a direct experience exchange between policy and decision-makers can expand the pool of solutions available in different countries.

Work

The question of equal recognition of the work of women and men in rural areas, and particularly in agriculture, emerges as crosscutting both the domain of public policy and social stereotypes (mentalities), as well as the transgresses national borders influencing the EU policy making. The main issue highlighted by various types of participants in the focus group from various countries was that of unequal work recognition leading to unequal pay for women and men. The gender stereotypes continue to constitute barriers to access good jobs for women. In turn, this creates additional insecurities for women

when it also translates into a lack of decent pensions for women and social support. One example:

“There is an opinion that there is less money for women because they are less competitive. Why do women have lower salaries for the same job? [T]he women are not so competitive. Because they have other responsibilities. At home, at school, with children” (Researcher, Czech Republic)

Despite the slowly increasing equity in domestic work division between women and men, the slow change in mentalities about stereotype gender roles also impacts the distribution of domestic work. Participants highlighted the need for a fairer, more equitable domestic work distribution between men and women.

The overall cautionary tale here is that lack of proper public policy assessment from the perspective of gender impact also leads to public policies which hinder women, as generally there are few life-oriented public policies. To paraphrase one of the participants, there is a need to engage concomitantly in gender proofing policies and rural proofing policies to tackle this systemic complex issue.

4.3 WHAT APPEAR AS THE MOST CRITICAL ISSUES FOR FUTURE POLICY TO ADDRESS?

Gender equality

Participants in the focus groups shared that the topic of gender equality is still a central one. However, approaches to reach it vary significantly from country to country. These varied approaches rely in part on internalized gender stereotypes and a patriarchal mentality. Beliefs from others that “women are not interested in politics” were still shared during the focus groups. There is a perception that personal success is possible without policy assistance, particularly given lack of support for women within the current public policies. There is significant distrust in public policies and laws as an instrument to change mentalities and gender stereotypes. This leads to the idea that positive discrimination on gender grounds can be counterproductive.

There is consensus on the limitations of legal and public policies impact on gender equality, pointing to need to transform structurally the mindset and mentalities. Education – both formal and informal is a key factor in tackling this issue. The participants perceived as limited the effectiveness of gender equality initiatives, particularly in politics. While gender equality and women's empowerment are encouraged through various projects, there's a lack of coherent meaningful policies and actions to bring about substantial change.

Governance / Institutional

The picture becomes clearer however as gender equality is applied to specific areas. As such, in terms of governance, the issue of women's representation becomes evident. The preference of the participants in the focus group is for inclusive gender participation

in decision-making, rather than women-only decision-making spaces. At the same time, participants were realistic in highlighting that the system tends to conserve its status quo, hence having only a few women in high-profile decision-making roles might not make a profound change in terms of gender equality and women's representation in governing structures.

In terms of values reflected by the governance mechanism, a disconnect between the decision-makers and the represented citizens becomes visible in all countries participating in the focus groups. One of the systemic disconnect is related to the mode of production and consumption: while the dominant model is that of competitive economy, based on extraction and profit, many women innovators shared they prefer the social enterprise one, more sustainable due to limited growth. A clear example mentioned by a participant was that of prioritizing expenses and investments in the military industry over more sustainable agricultural practices.

The local administration is also seen as struggling in various countries, including in terms of lacking training and adequate funding. The overlap between governance structures and responsibilities chips away at its efficiency and creates many grey areas for the citizens. Together with a high volume of work – especially for those working in farming – this directly leads to underrepresentation in decision-making: *“You are too busy working making a living. This leads to under representation” (Practitioner, IE)*. This leads to missed innovation opportunities on the one hand, and to areas of overlap on the other, showing a lack of understanding and responsibility for their community impact. The perception of the participants in the focus groups is that local development work has suffered due to insufficient core funding and lacking frontline personnel who can address community issues effectively, with the real need being for knowledgeable individuals within local development organizations to navigate the system.

In turn, the disconnect between governing institutions and the population leads to certain sectors not benefiting from the care they would need: as such, policies targeting youth, and most specifically that support and connect them with their desired activities are missing. Rural development policies can also be included here: the overlaps and lack of prioritizing rural development strategies and funding distribution is directly impacting the rural infrastructures and available social and public services, as we have seen.

The lack of coherency from EU level to national, regional and local levels further adds to the conundrum. The EU model of civic consultation is seen as a top-down approach which is not embraced by national governments. This translates into input from public consultation not being sufficiently included in policy making and policy implementation, due to lack of representation in decision making of various groups affected by the decisions.

At the same time, participants noted that this can create apathy, a lack of civic responsibility and action, leading to an overall lack of empowerment to contribute to public decision-making. Development policies from a rural perspective should involve inclusive consultations with impacted communities, integrating interconnected sectors

like environment and transport, addressing green agenda challenges, and ensuring flexibility to adapt to local needs while empowering diverse representatives, including women innovators and young people.

Policy design and implementation

Rural development is seen as lacking in most countries in terms of core funding as well as in terms of strategy, vision and technical capacities of the local administration. This lack of strategic vision for rural development deprives rural communities of plans adapted to the specific local context, and an approach which takes in consideration all social categories (youth, elderly, women, etc.). While there are different projects and programs supporting women in the various countries, as well local policies targeting women in some of the cases, including measures in place to address gender/domestic violence, the lack of overarching vision makes it complicated for their combined impact to be evaluated or produce long lasting change in terms of policy design:

“Most policies developed throughout history were meant by and for men and do not address the special needs of women nor women’s business characteristics. Policies should be gendered. E.g. policies often focus on productivity and quick developments, but this is not what happens, particularly in the case of many women-led businesses. Businesses take a long time to grow and develop and often they remain just small and that is fine and should be supported.”
(Researcher, IE)

A significant area for improvement is the lack of overarching public policy addressing women's needs, compounded by limited political awareness, slow policy changes, inadequate support for youth in rural decision-making, and superficial approaches to gender equality in both public and private sectors. Change in policy design is seen as possible by the focus group participants only through collaboration with governments and advocacy by civil society organisations.

Policy implementation faces critical challenges, as excellent policies and ideas often fail to translate into grassroots impact, leaving issues like succession crises in farming unaddressed, while institutions monitoring equality lack effective enforcement and initiative execution. Together with a change in mentalities, to understand how policy design for gender equality can be done, public policy and laws currently regarding agriculture, entrepreneurship and rural development being implemented should be closely monitored and evaluated in terms of impact on different categories of women, including especially rural women and young rural women.

Table 25: Potential benchmarks for agriculture, rural development and entrepreneurship policy impact assessment on women, rural women and young rural

Targeted action	Examples
Public institutions implement Gender Impact Assessments with breakdowns for rural women to improve gender equality through public policy.	Based on the Gender Impact Assessment by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE , 2017), this action proposes to expand this type of analysis to include breakdowns for rural women and young rural women (as well as other relevant criteria such as income, education level, family status, etc) in order to improve the policy design in the areas of agriculture, rural development and entrepreneurship in terms of gender equality.

4.4 CONCLUSION AND SPECIFIC SUGGESTIONS FOR POLICY

The initial benchmarking statements (Annex 2) presented in FLIARA D1.5 provided a starting point in framing the analysis of topics discussed during the focus groups. Reflections on the statements based on the findings emerging from the CoP workshops are discussed in Section 6.1, where they are brought together with observations based on Section 2 and 3. Also to complement the benchmarking statements, the focus groups also collected policy suggestions made during the activities. These are grouped in the table below and merit special consideration as they were put forward by women already leading sustainable rural and agriculture innovation:

Table 26. Policy suggestions of the innovative women as shared during the CoP workshops

Policy Suggestion	Challenge(s)/opportunities it responds to
EU funds municipalities that are getting depopulated: make them hubs for creativity and local development rather than just focusing on tourism, especially it would be important to implement strategies to not sell all properties in rural areas to foreigners.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural defunding • Rural depopulation • Multidimensional sustainable rural development • Preservation of preserving local cultural specificity
Microgrants for startups led by women	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excessive bureaucracy • Burdensome reporting • Harness the potential of women-led innovation in rural areas

Tax exemptions/fiscal incentives for women starting or running SMEs in rural areas

- Clear criteria for size of enterprise to qualify (returns, number of employees), exemption value according to needs
- Harness the potential of women-led innovation in rural areas

5. KEY ISSUES FOR THE NEXT COP POLICY DESIGN AND ASSESSMENT WORKSHOPS

Throughout our analysis of data from WP1, WP3 and WP4 we kept in mind the local, regional, national and/or EU level benchmarking. However, certain issues appeared as crosscutting and impacting at all levels. Areas of promise are identified, as well as current gaps. While our starting point was better support for women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas, the findings in this report show that the issues brought forward by our research go beyond sectorial policies for agriculture, for example, and have an impact on rural development overall. Similarly, the issue of gender equality transgresses the area of rural development, pointing to general issues with policy design, implementation, monitoring and impact assessment. These issues merit to further be addressed within the remaining T4.3 activities, namely two policy design workshops which will take place in Italy and Sweden respectively.

5.1 CROSS-CUTTING ISSUES

A combination of targeted and universal measures

A range of targeted measures towards women are identified in this report, shown in the targeted actions discussed across the different tables. There are however also some targeted actions suggested that do not target women directly. Rather, these targeted actions point to more systemic barriers which affect women innovators disproportionately. Additionally, innovative women themselves display high degrees of autonomy and a self-empowered mindset which allows them to navigate the different challenges they encounter at different levels.

Better supports for women-led innovation in rural areas and in agriculture should take into consideration the specific needs of the women, while identifying the systemic barriers that need to be tackled concomitantly. This raises the question of if systemic barriers are addressed effectively, public policy supporting women's innovation may not necessarily need to include measures targeting women directly but rather employ an integrated, place-based, intersectional approach which allows for a comprehensive understanding of opportunities and challenges in a specific context. This comprehensive understanding includes evidence of the interplay between EU, national and local level policies in creating or eliminating systemic barriers for women innovators and potential for improvement. Section 2 points to how Sweden and Finland for example have laws that create a more systematic focus on gender equality in all policies and at all levels of it. This question remains open and is one that merits further attention through FLIARA next steps.

The policy support system itself can be a barrier to women-led innovation

The policy support system, while designed to foster innovation and development, can pose significant barriers to women-led innovation, particularly in rural and farm contexts. Challenges appear across different stages of the policy life cycle, such as design, implementation, and monitoring. In the design phase, a lack of gender-sensitive

approaches and an overarching vision for rural development often excludes the specific needs and dynamics of women-led enterprises. Also relating to policy design, when high level objectives include gender-related issues the strong filtering down to actions on the ground can also be a challenge. Policy implementation is hindered by excessive bureaucracy, inflexible funding criteria, and limited accessibility to support and funding programs, sometimes deterring women from applying or fully engaging. Policy monitoring frameworks can fail to include a sufficient gender breakdown of data, making it difficult to assess the uptake and effectiveness of measures for women.

Governance structures further add to these issues. Across various countries, CoP focus group participants noted that decision-making processes often fail to represent the diversity of rural communities, with women and youth particularly underrepresented. Addressing these barriers related to governance structures suggests a more systemic transformation: gender-inclusive governance mechanisms, streamlined administrative processes, better data integration in policy monitoring, and comprehensive, context-sensitive and place-based strategies that prioritise collaboration between governments, local organisations, and civil society, including women's networks.

The important role of place-based and locally-led supports

Across all levels, the data collected shows that governance must prioritise inclusivity, accountability, and responsiveness to rural communities' needs. A coherent and integrated approach from the EU to national, regional, and local levels is necessary to ensure policy alignment and effective resource distribution. Inclusive consultations with impacted communities, particularly women and youth, should be central to the policy-making process. Participants highlighted the need for governance systems to embrace the interconnected nature of sectors like rural development, sustainability, and transportation. By addressing these governance challenges holistically, policymakers can create a supportive ecosystem that empowers women-led innovation and strengthens rural communities.

Strengthen rural sustainability and rural economy renewal with women-led rural and farm innovation as a lever

Women-led rural and farm innovation plays a critical role in advancing rural sustainability and renewing rural economies, yet it faces numerous challenges alongside clear opportunities. Many innovations are smaller in scale, slower to develop, or focus on creating social, cultural, and environmental benefits rather than solely economic ones. These dynamics require targeted financial and policy support that accommodates diverse growth patterns and less conventional forms of agriculture, such as organic, regenerative, or biodynamic farming. Section 2 that draws on the FLIARA Policy Assessment (D1.3) points to a range of potential targeted actions (see Table 8) that could more indirectly support women-led innovation, such as improved supportive frameworks for short food supply chains, care farming and social enterprise. Section 3 that draws on the FLIARA case studies points the important role of women-led innovation in renewal of the farm and rural economy through increasing a focus on rural economy

diversification and farm multifunctionality. Programs like LEADER are particularly valued for their ability to integrate sustainability goals with innovation, but CoP focus group (Section 4) participants emphasised the need for broader accessibility, better communication of funding opportunities, and reduced bureaucratic hurdles. Addressing systemic barriers such as insufficiently adequate public policies on entrepreneurship and rural infrastructure can potentially significantly impact women's ability to drive sustainable innovation across all dimensions, economic, ecological, social, and cultural.

Opportunities for women-led innovation are deeply rooted in the untapped potential of rural environments and the unique perspectives women bring as rural change agents. The case studies from across the FLIARA countries highlight how women are leveraging local resources to enhance rural multifunctionality, preserve cultural heritage, and promote community cohesion. Through social enterprises, technological advancements, or environmental innovations like circular economy concepts, women are demonstrating their capacity to address pressing local needs, empower marginalised groups, and drive sustainable transformative change. By fostering such initiatives with tailored support and targeted funding, policymakers and local communities can harness the energy and creativity of women innovators to revitalise rural areas, improve sustainability, and build resilient, diverse rural economies.

Address traditional gender norms and stereotypes

Overcoming traditional gender norms and stereotypes remains a significant obstacle to achieving gender equality and advancing women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas. As emerged in some of the WP3 case study findings, deeply rooted patriarchal attitudes and a scepticism towards women engaged in non-traditional activities or entering rural areas as newcomers continue to create barriers. These challenges can discourage collaboration and prevent women from being fully recognised as leaders and innovators in rural areas and in agriculture. From the CoP focus groups, significant distrust in the ability of public institutions to enact public policies to effectively address these entrenched mentalities was noted, highlighting instead the need for broader cultural and structural shifts driven by education and awareness. As highlighted from existing and new policy measure ideas emerging from the WP3 case studies (Section 3) and wider policy assessment (Section 2), media initiatives, visibility campaigns, and community platforms were seen as valuable tools for breaking down stereotypes and showcasing the vital contributions of rural women, encouraging others to follow their example. These efforts must be supported by well-designed policies and programmes that address gender inequality in a more comprehensive and coordinated way.

Relevant opportunities exist to transform perceptions and unlock the potential of women-led rural innovation. Leveraging education to dismantle stereotypes, coupled with targeted initiatives to build self-confidence and entrepreneurial capacity, can empower women to break free from traditional roles. The FLIARA case studies highlight the importance of life-stage factors in enabling rural innovation, suggesting that policies should account for age-related barriers and opportunities, especially for women in mid-life stages. Furthermore, rural newcomers and women innovators have demonstrated

their ability to challenge conventional norms, serving as catalysts for sustainable, innovative change in their communities. By fostering inclusive narratives, improving access to resources, and celebrating success stories, stakeholders can create an environment where women are not only seen as equal participants but as driving forces of rural innovation and sustainable development.

Harness and enhance digital and technological skills and opportunities

Digitalisation offers significant opportunities and challenges for women farm innovators in rural areas. On the one hand, access to broadband and digital tools has enabled the women to leverage social media, e-commerce platforms, and web presence to support marketing, sales, and business growth, as shown in various case studies across Europe and illustrated in Section 3. Digital technologies also foster connectivity, networking, and access to valuable resources like training and funding opportunities. However, challenges persist, particularly regarding digital literacy and skills development, which remain unevenly distributed, especially in rural and less connected areas. The fast-evolving nature of digitalisation, including emerging technologies like artificial intelligence, underscores the need for ongoing training and education to address gaps and mitigate risks. By addressing these challenges, women innovators can fully harness the transformative potential of digital technologies to enhance their entrepreneurial success and rural development.

Broadband access is a critical enabler of rural innovation, facilitating efficiency improvements, digital marketing, and broader market reach. While some regions, such as Sweden and the Netherlands, report reliable broadband as a cornerstone of innovation, other areas like Spain and Romania highlight limited infrastructure as a significant barrier. National policies, such as Ireland's National Broadband Plan, emphasise the importance of expanding high-quality internet services to bridge these gaps. Ensuring universal broadband availability is essential for empowering rural innovators, particularly women, to leverage digital opportunities and drive sustainable development in rural areas.

Advancing Education and Skills Training for Women Innovators

Women innovators highlight access to training, education, gaining skills and more broadly building their capacities as one of the underlying issues impacting their capacity to innovate, as particularly illustrated in the FLIARA case study analysis (Section 3) and CoP workshop findings (Section 4). This impacts their capacity to innovate in particular areas (e.g. technology) and also more broadly engage with the funding support system and its complexities. They face distinct challenges and opportunities in accessing information, training, and education in the rural contexts they inhabit. Key barriers include limited access to formal and informal education in vital areas such as finance, digital literacy, and entrepreneurship, together with geographic and socioeconomic constraints. The opportunities that exist concomitantly are to develop targeted training programs, reform education systems to integrate entrepreneurship and gender equality, and foster peer-to-peer learning networks. By investing in digital infrastructure, enhancing access

to technological tools, and addressing systemic biases, policies can unlock the untapped potential of women innovators. Strengthening mentorship initiatives, supporting lifelong learning, and promoting inclusive, practice-based learning models like demonstration farms are crucial steps toward achieving sustainable, gender-inclusive innovation.

5.2 ISSUES RELATED TO SPECIFIC BARRIERS TO WOMEN-LED RURAL AND FARM INNOVATION

Entrepreneurship and Access to Finance

Women's innovative entrepreneurship in rural areas faces significant challenges, particularly in navigating complex legal, financial, and policy environments, regardless of if the domain of activity is agriculture or rural development. The key barriers include inadequate and/or insufficient training, limited access to networks, and insufficiently tailored support at different business development stages. These are composed of restrictive tax and legal frameworks, gender biases in access to funding, and limited funding options for smaller-scale enterprises, innovations aiming for social impact or projects implementing alternative economic models. Additionally, rural entrepreneurs often struggle with bureaucratic hurdles and lack of coherent, accessible information on available supports. Many innovative women shared that they rely on personal savings or family loans to start their innovative projects, which creates an uneven playing field.

At the same time, there are significant opportunities to support women entrepreneurs through targeted initiatives. Programmes like mentorship schemes, incremental funding strategies, and innovation incubators tailored to women's needs have shown promise in various countries. Simplified, direct access to comprehensive information through digital one-stop-shop platforms or local support hubs can address knowledge gaps. Enhancing access to diverse funding sources, including grants, loans, and non-traditional methods like crowdfunding and microcredits, can empower women-led businesses. Policy adjustments that recognise rural enterprises' unique contributions to social cohesion and sustainability, coupled with gender-sensitive impact evaluations, can create a supportive ecosystem for rural women innovators and further foster sustainable rural development.

Networks and Peer Support

To foster women-led rural innovation, there is a clear need to ensure women have access to strong and diverse networks, particularly peer support networks, as these play a pivotal role in knowledge-sharing, problem-solving, resource access, and advocacy. Opportunities exist to create targeted networks for women innovators, as highlighted in the Netherlands, Spain and Italy, while also ensuring integration into broader, mixed-gender networks to avoid silos and promote inclusivity. Addressing barriers like geographical constraints and limited access to specialised skills training, particularly in alternative sustainable agricultures, is essential for enhancing the capacity of these networks. Peer-to-peer learning and mentorship programs, such as ACORNS (Ireland), demonstrate the potential of practice-based learning to bridge skills gaps.

While family and community networks are valuable enablers, tailored services—such as childcare and parental leave support—are crucial to ensure that all women, including single mothers and those without robust personal networks, can access opportunities for innovation. Strengthening self-organised, bottom-up initiatives and providing policy support for collaborative spaces can further empower women to overcome systemic challenges and drive meaningful change.

Rural development – access to infrastructure and services

Supporting women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas requires addressing systemic challenges related to infrastructure, services, and societal norms in rural communities. Key opportunities include enhancing access to quality childcare, parental leave, and education services, which empower women to balance work and family commitments. In terms of rural development, integrated transport systems and improved public infrastructure can mitigate physical isolation and facilitate rural business development. Challenges include addressing the gendered impact of insufficient social services, such as care for children and the elderly, and fostering self-confidence and visibility among women innovators. Collaborative policy measures and innovative use of funds, alongside strong local and regional initiatives, are essential to create an inclusive environment for rural women's economic and social participation, which in turn can foster more innovation.

Barriers specific to women-led farm innovation

The current policy support system, although designed to promote innovation and development from the EU level to the local ones, often presents significant barriers to women-led agricultural innovation. This is due to bureaucratic rigidity, restrictive funding criteria, and insufficient focus on gender equity at all stages, from policy design to implementation and monitoring. These barriers disproportionately affect women innovators, particularly in rural and agricultural sectors, where traditional gender norms and economic disparities already limit opportunities. The complexity and time-intensive nature of applying for funding, creates hurdles for women who may lack the necessary capacity or resources, or may be already overworked on their farms. Furthermore, the current support system can fail to adequately account for opportunities related to sustainable environmental, economic, cultural and social practices, which women are more likely to employ, and overlook the intersectional challenges (e.g. age, class) faced by female innovators. These systemic obstacles perpetuate economic inequalities, marginalise sustainable agricultural practices, and prevent efforts to achieve gender-balanced representation in policy and decision-making spaces in rural areas and in relation to agriculture.

The opportunities identified go towards reimagining and restructuring support systems to better serve women-led innovations in agriculture. Introducing mentorship programs, innovation incubators, and targeted financial instruments such as microloans or gender-specific grants could empower women to overcome skill and resource gaps. Additionally, developing policies that prioritise gender-sensitive land access, including reforms to

inheritance laws and long-term leasing arrangements, would address critical barriers to entry for women who wish to innovate in agriculture. By fostering inclusive decision-making and amplifying the voices of women in farming networks, these measures can reshape perceptions of agriculture and rural life, highlighting their vital role in food security and environmental stewardship. In doing so, public policy can not only mitigate systemic inequities but also unlock the transformative potential of women-led innovations to drive sustainable development in rural areas.

Domestic work distribution and work equity

Women innovators still face significant challenges related to unequal work recognition, and entrenched gender stereotypes, both when engaged in agriculture or in the rural areas more generally. These issues are made up by a rather inequitable distribution of domestic responsibilities, limited access to childcare in most rural areas of the EU, and inadequate rural services such as public transport and healthcare. Women in rural areas can experience barriers to innovation due to insufficient parental leave policies, lack of broadband access, and structural obstacles that disproportionately affect their ability to engage in entrepreneurship or public decision-making. These constraints not only hinder women's professional growth but also perpetuate economic insecurities, such as inadequate pensions and limited business opportunities.

Policies promoting and supporting shared domestic responsibilities, gender equality education, and family-friendly welfare systems (like Sweden and Romania's long shared parental leave) can pave the way for change. Digitalisation offers significant potential to enable flexible working arrangements and broaden market access for rural women entrepreneurs. Leveraging family and community networks as sources of social capital, alongside targeted policy reforms such as improved childcare services and infrastructure, can enhance rural women's capacity to innovate. Addressing these systemic barriers through comprehensive and inclusive public policies is essential to unlocking the full potential of women innovators in rural and other underrepresented contexts and foster gender-inclusive innovation.

5.3 CONCLUSION

Our analysis highlighted crosscutting issues impacting policy for rural and farm women innovators at all levels, revealing gaps and opportunities beyond sectorial policies, with gender equality and rural development pointing to broader challenges in policy design, implementation and assessment.

- This report highlights key cross-cutting issues essential for better supporting women-led sustainable innovation in agriculture and rural areas.
- It underscores the need for a balanced approach combining targeted and universal measures, addressing systemic barriers within the policy support system, and leveraging place-based and locally-led supports and initiatives.

- Strengthening rural sustainability and revitalising rural economies and communities require harnessing women-led innovations as a transformative lever.
- The report emphasises dismantling traditional gender norms and stereotypes, enhancing digital and technological skills, and advancing education and skills training to empower women innovators and create a more inclusive and dynamic rural development ecosystem.
- Additionally, this report also identified critical barriers to women-led rural and farm innovation, including challenges in entrepreneurship and access to finance, limitations around networks and peer support, inadequate rural infrastructure and services, specific obstacles faced by women in agricultural innovation, and inequitable domestic work distribution and work equity. This emphasises the need for systemic reforms, together with targeted actions, to foster gender-inclusive, sustainable rural development.

The topics identified as relevant from an initial benchmarking perspective will be further addressed within the remaining activities within T4.3, and further refined to feed into policy briefs and policy recommendations in WP5 more widely. Sustainability remains an underlying topic and intention for the innovative initiatives analysed, which in turn impacts the perspective of the innovators on the policy and legal framework in which they are inserted.

6. KEY BENCHMARKING FINDINGS

This report has focused on exploring what are the potential benchmarks for gender benchmarking policy on its performance to support women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. This is one crucial and important step towards gender benchmarking, but there are further key steps to take that will be explored in our final Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3). Further to this the FLIARA knowledge base, its research findings (WP2, WP3), upcoming CoP workshops (WP4) and wider Policy Design and Assessment work (WP5, particularly T5.1), can also further help FLIARA assess the priority and shape given to any benchmark.

If benchmarking indicators are derived from existing policy they do not account for major gaps, as well as the potential for new and innovative policies and support measures. FLIARA's Initial Benchmarking Report (D1.5) warned against deriving benchmarks only from policy for this reason. This is why we bring a number of different types of knowledge together in this report, the policy-relevant findings of the FLIARA case studies (Section 3) and the findings from workshops held at the FLIARA CoP Network events in Ireland and Slovenia. This gives us a comprehensive base of evidence upon which to take our next steps. One key step is to decide what set of benchmarks we will put together to form our final guidelines for gender benchmarking policy on its performance to support women-led innovation in farming and rural areas.

In this section we reflect on and compile a set of wider issues to guide the process of deciding what our final benchmarking indicators should be and how they are applied to benchmark. This is done in two ways. First in Section 6.1 we reflect more pragmatically on the methodology and process of benchmarking and developing guidelines for a gender benchmarking framework on women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. Then in Sections 6.2 and 6.3 some wider reflections and potential points of debate for further consideration are outlined.

6.1 SOME REFLECTIONS ON THE INITIAL GOOD PRACTICE POLICY BENCHMARK STATEMENTS

FLIARA's Initial Benchmarking Report (D1.5) presented a set of initial good practice benchmark statements intended to act as potential reference points for good practice (see Annex 2). They emerged from the FLIARA policy assessment (D1.3) as a starting point for what might be understood as main themes, topics or domains for a benchmarking framework. This was also with the idea that with further work and refinements informed by emerging FLIARA results, they could provide some basis for benchmarking tools. This process starts in this deliverable and will be continued on our final Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3). As part of this work, we will also reflect on if 'benchmark statements' are indeed the best approach to pin-pointing specific domains for benchmarking. As part of our final Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3) the review that is carried out can also focus specifically on assessing how this aspect of benchmarking is approached in other methods.

Limitations and benefits of a one-dimensional benchmarking framework

Using a tool such as 'benchmark statements' to assist benchmarking around key themes does present a one-dimensional benchmarking framework and has pros and cons. For example, a very simple approach would result in specific indicators being linked to each benchmark statement that allows for its assessment. Annex 3 provides an example of how certain 'targeted actions' identified in tables throughout this report could fit under the theme of a benchmark statement. This example is not presented with the intention that all of these indicators should be used to benchmark policy. Rather it aims to be illustrative of the potential link between overarching benchmark statement topics and indicators that could be used to assess and compare policies.

Building sustainability into a benchmarking framework

The initial benchmarking statements did not address sustainability directly or consider the dimensions of analysis used in D3.3 (ecological, social, economic, cultural). These dimensions were used to categorise the innovation led by rural women – however, the data collected within WP1, WP3 and the CoP focus groups shows that challenges and opportunities faced by women innovating in agriculture and rural areas are crosscutting these dimensions, regardless of their specific sustainability dimension. While specific challenges exist for different dimensions of sustainable innovation, topics such as improvement to public policies regarding entrepreneurship or rural infrastructure have a significant impact on all of them. During the CoP focus group, the topic of sustainability was brought up by the participants themselves, and particularly by the practitioners/innovative women participating. This validates the findings in D3.3 that rural innovative women are driven by an intention to innovate sustainably and take into consideration sustainability dimensions when designing their innovations.

More broadly, the findings of this report can be used to directly reflect on the benchmark statements, if and how they might be taken forward. This will also be considered further in FLIARA's final Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3). Below we begin reflect on the statements directly based on the findings of this report. The gaps not accounted for in particular need further reflection. The statements are in italics and the goals they were grouped within in bold (see also Annex 2 for the full list).

Goals: 'Close gender gaps in farming and the rural labour market' and 'Achieve equal participation in rural and farm innovation'

Women are a target group in rural and farm policy. Data collected via the CoP focus groups regarding this statement highlighted that positive discrimination is not necessarily perceived as a desirable way of advancing gender equality as it dims the personal merits of some of the innovative women. In some contexts, such as Finland and Sweden, targeted measures are generally not taken due to national laws, as highlighted in Section 2. Debate surrounding directly targeted measures is also highlighted in Section 3. The FLIARA Conceptual Framework however argues that until gender equality is achieved positive discrimination should be considered. In addition to these issues, adding this as a key benchmark statement creates challenges to compare across countries because of different fundamental political approaches to tackling gender inequality.

Rural and farm policy include specific measures for achieving gender equality: The need for measures to tackle gender equality in rural and farm policy is seen almost throughout this report. However an issue with this statement appears more with its potential overlap and lack of refinement. This benchmark statement links for example closely with the first statement discussed above. It potentially overlaps with it and similar measures/potential benchmarks outlined in the example in Annex 3 could be used to benchmark in relation to this statement. These arguments are also relevant to this statement: *Supports for rural and farm innovation address the specific disadvantages women face.*

Supports for rural and farm innovation are not uncertain or volatile: This statement is potentially too narrow and could be expanded to capture a key issue identified across the different sections of this report relating to issues discussed around how the policy support system itself can be a barrier to women benefiting from supports. For example, issues related to bureaucracy emerged in Section 3 and Section 4.

Supports for rural and farm innovation harness underutilised or untapped areas of opportunity related to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas: For this statement the CoP focus group data showed that the practitioners and other stakeholders agree that innovative rural women tend to employ very innovative, more sustainable and socially-oriented agricultural practices, which is not currently reflected in the support they receive. The discussion of how women-led innovation can enhance the renewal, sustainability and multifunctionality of rural areas and farming in Section 3 also underlines the importance of benchmarking focusing on the topic embedded in this statement.

Policy does not treat women as a homogenous group and targets the specific needs of particular groups of women in relation to rural and farm innovation: This statement remains one that appears key. Section 2 highlights this as a policy gap and Section 3 also reinforces this point. Further expanding issues related to women's more specific needs on particular stages of their innovation journey as a sub-topic or new topic also merits further consideration.

Policies exist that are community-led and place-based that allow for the specific needs of women in particular places to be addressed through a bottom-up approach: The participants in the CoP focus group generally agreed that transformation towards more visibility, support and scaling of women-led innovation in agriculture and rural areas is compound of top-down policy changes, deep mentality changes, and bottom-up community-based initiatives. This statement thus stands true for a relevant public policy benchmarking and future policy recommendations. The case study findings in Section 3 also further underline the relevance of this topic for benchmarking.

Goal: Achieve equal empowerment of women

Adequate opportunities exist for women to influence the decisions that impact them & Adequate cooperation and networking opportunities exist for women supporting participation and success in women-led innovation: The bottom-up, place based, community-led initiatives are conditioned by structural access to education, infrastructure, economic opportunities and public/social services. However, this also impacts the opportunities that women have to engage in public consultation and local decision-making. At the same time, organising their communities and creating women

networks (but not only) is frequently an essential part of their innovations – and thus becomes a steppingstone for self-organizing to more effectively participate in decision-making. As such, these two statements go together. General existing evidence and the CoP focus group data converge here in showing that rural women generally do not have equal access to influence the decisions that impact them and it is urgent for this to be addressed.

Adequate supports exist to build skills and innovation capacities supporting participation and success in women-led innovation. The importance of supports enabling women-led entrepreneurship and innovation is a key topic discussed across all of the three main sections of this report. This looks without doubt a key benchmark statement that could also merit having further development through expanding a number of sub-topics that are also benchmarked within this part of a benchmarking framework (e.g. access to finance, networks, education and skills).

Policies address increasing the visibility of women-led innovation and challenge gender stereotypes related to work life and professions: This appears another central benchmark statement and area of key importance for benchmarking with issues relating to this discussed across all of the three main sections of this report.

Goal: Address gender related work-life conflicts

Certain and stable support services exist that assist work and leisure life balance & Certain and stable supports exist that assist work and family life balance & Policies address features of professional life so that they do not discourage women's participation and success in innovation: These statements embed important issues related to balancing work and life demands that emerged across the different sections of this report. They are areas where the 'targeted actions' and examples highlighted in the different tables are fewer. This raises the question of whether they could in some way merge as part of a benchmarking framework and may not require three separate statements to account for them.

6.2 WIDER GUIDELINES FOR NEXT STEPS

Define 'gender benchmarking' more clearly and deeply

Our Initial Benchmarking Guidelines (D1.5) pointed to the fact that benchmarking is a term used broadly, such as defined by Fagerberg (2001; 2003) simply as the systematic comparison of policies and learning from the results to improve policy, or more narrowly, as seen in Table 27. Neither definition contradicts the other, one describes the core principles underpinning benchmarking, the other is more pragmatic and hints at the process and method followed in this systematic comparison. It is also important to draw clear boundaries between benchmarking and other methods of policy assessment. If we do not define benchmarking clearly, lines become blurred between other methods (e.g. gender proofing, gender policy impact assessment). Some examples of different methods are also outlined in Table 27. In this context, the wide range of potential

benchmarks identified in this report underlines the importance of setting out more clearly the scope and process of the final FLIARA benchmarking guidelines.

Table 27: Definitions of methods of gender-related policy assessment

Step	Explanation
Benchmarking	The establishment of criterion, standard or reference point against which to establish targets and measure progress.
Gender audit	The analysis and evaluation of policies, programmes and institutions in terms of how they apply gender-related criteria.
Gender Impact Assessment	Examining policy proposals to see whether they will affect women and men differently, with a view to adapting these proposals to make sure that discriminatory effects are neutralised and that gender equality is promoted.
Gender planning	An active approach to planning which takes gender as a key variable or criterion and which seeks to incorporate an explicit gender dimension into policy or action.
Gender proofing	A check carried out on any policy proposal to ensure that any potential gender discriminatory effect arising from that policy have been avoided and that gender equality is promoted.

Source: One Hundred Words for Equality, EC, 1998

Explore the potential for a comprehensive, adaptable benchmarking framework

As highlighted in FLIARA's Initial Benchmarking Report (D1.5) issues in national contexts, as well as their policy and legal frameworks differ, which potentially calls for a flexible benchmarking framework. Therefore a 'pick and mix' of benchmarks could be useful where particular benchmarks are selected from a set of domains that must be covered. Further to this, potentially certain domains could be focused on alone to construct thematic benchmarking focused on specific topics such as access to finance or benchmark in a more cross-cutting way such as benchmarking of supports that target different stages of the women-led innovation journey. A flexible framework could also allow room for construction of different types of benchmarking tools, with a larger range of indicators and domains used in deeper more comprehensive assessments and a small number of indicators in rapid benchmarking assessments. The extensive list of potential actions and therefore benchmarks also provide potential room to construct specific and tailored benchmarking frameworks for national benchmarking that compares regional or local levels.

Still, there are potentially cross-cutting issues of wider relevance

Are there essential elements for any policy benchmarking framework aiming to assess issues related to gender equality? For example, the grand challenges we face as a society today such as gender equality and sustainability issues appear something that any policy benchmarking exercise should include. Another issue is the policy process itself and should any benchmarking framework include indicators that assess specific policy principles, such as if measures are in place to assist people to engage with the

support process and the complexity of assessment criteria for supports and the application process.

Consider if a scoring system is needed, in some cases

Our Initial Benchmarking Guidelines (D1.5) pointed to the challenges of benchmarking national policy frameworks across the EU because of core differences in governance structures, law and policy. Potentially to overcome this a system of tiered benchmarks, where some are marked as fundamental, while others can be scored based on their national relevance, could be a useful approach. As part of our final Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3) FLIARA will review the current state of gender benchmarking policy and particular focus should be placed on identifying if and how scoring systems are used as part of existing approaches.

6.3 OTHER REFLECTIONS ON POLICY BENCHMARKING

Finally in this section we present some wider reflections and arising questions from this report's assessment. These raise important issues that merit further consideration and are intended as more provoking questions to shape our wider thinking as we return to our final benchmarking activities and work on our final Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3).

The value of gender benchmarking depends on the level at which benchmarking is applied?

The policy process has many layers and complexities. Benchmarking policy strategies and plans is one level at which benchmarking can be applied to assess support for women-led rural and farm innovation. However, policy promises are not the full story as the discussion on the trickle down of CAP S08 (Section 2) has shown. Benchmarking the results and impacts of policies is a different proposition potentially needing a phased approach to benchmarking that links initial objectives to results achieved. But perhaps this is more than what the core principle of 'benchmarking' embodies, hence this again points to the importance of clear definition and drawing of boundaries.

Given that benchmarking is a comparative process, is it even really possible at the cross-national level?

Given the range of potential actions emerging from this report, and benchmarks that could be derived from them, it does appear that gender benchmarking policy needs a comprehensive framework crossing policy areas. However, in some national contexts some issues may be more important policy gaps than others based on the extent of the challenges at national levels. We can only talk here about potentially desirable and promising policy practices because transferring policy measures and initiatives from different contexts is a tricky process. Design of any benchmarking framework should keep this key issue in mind and assess it in relation to all parts of the proposed framework.

Is the question ‘what are the benchmarks’ one that merits significant further attention?

There are a multi-faceted range of issues of policy relevance impacting women-led innovation identified in this report. An important outcome of FLIARA in itself could be the identification of a set of final benchmarks for gender benchmarking of policy in relation to supporting women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. ‘Counting what counts’ is really what matters, so the question of what are the benchmarks is a very important one.

7. CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

The report illustrates how the issues impacting the capacity for women-led rural and farm innovation are diverse. This then raises a range of areas in need of policy attention in relation to potential for policy improvements, as well as for benchmarking to start to assess the extent of policy practice in these areas.

What is outlined in this report also needs further assessment regarding how the potential benchmarks identified can work in the practice of benchmarking policy. The goals of benchmarking need to be clear, such as the scale of policy that is being benchmarked (e.g. local, regional, national and/or EU). The potential benchmarks outlined here can apply at different scales. For example, some of the potential benchmarks are national measures, while others are more local. They also represent different kinds of actions. For example, some of the potential benchmarks and examples are linked to specific ongoing policy measures, while others are shorter-term project type initiatives that have support from different funding schemes.

Differences in how to benchmark rural versus farm contexts in relation to women-led innovation also needs further consideration. Benchmarking could also potentially focus on particular issues at specific scales in the context of women-led rural and farm innovation, such as access to finance. Therefore, our benchmarking guidelines and final framework could present a range of benchmarks, with sub-sets used benchmark more specific issues. These are examples of issues to further work out which will be the focus of FLIARA's next benchmarking steps in WP5. This is where all of the assessment presented here will be drawn on to inform FLIARA's final Gender Benchmarking Report (D5.3).

REFERENCES

Cejudo, E., Navarro, F. and Cañete, J, A. 2020. Young and Women Entrepreneurs in Neo-endogenous Development, in eds. Eugenio Cejudo and Francisco Navarro *Neoendogenous Development in European Rural Areas: Results and Lessons*. Springer Geography: Switzerland.

D'Ambrogio, E., 2023. The gender dimension in cohesion policy. European Parliamentary Research Service Retrieved on 06/05/2024 from: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2023/739381/EPRS_ATA\(2023\)739381_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/ATAG/2023/739381/EPRS_ATA(2023)739381_EN.pdf)

EC, 1998. 100 Words for Equality: A Glossary of Terms on Equality between Women and Men. Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion. Retrieved on 25/05/2024 from <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7342d801-86cc-4f59-a71a-2ff7c0e04123>

EC, 2020. Recommendations to the Member States as regards their strategic plan for the Common Agricultural Policy. Retrieved on 04/05/2024 from <https://eurlex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0846>

EC, 2022. Proposed CAP Strategic Plans and Commission observations Summary overview for 27 Member States. Retrieved on 25/04/2024 from https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-07/csp-overview-28-plans-overviewjune-2022_en.pdf

EC, 2024. The long-term vision for the EU's rural areas: key achievements and ways forward. Retrieved on 19/05/2024 from https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legalcontent/EN/ALL/?uri=comnat:COM_2024_0450_FIN

ECA, 2022. LEADER and community-led local development facilitates local engagement but additional benefits still not sufficiently demonstrated. Special Report. Retrieved on 25/04/2024 from: <https://op.europa.eu/webpub/eca/special-reports/leader-10-2022/en/>

EIGE, 2017. Gender Impact Assessment - Gender Mainstreaming Toolkit. Retrieved on 9/12/2024 from https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/eige_gender_impact_assessment_gender_mainstreaming_toolkit.pdf

EU, 2021. Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of December 2021. Official Journal of the European Union. Retrieved on 30/05/2024 from <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2021/2115/oj>

European Parliament, 2022. Economic, social and territorial cohesion in the EU: the 8th Cohesion Report. European Parliament resolution of 15 September 2022 on economic, social and territorial cohesion in the EU. Retrieved on 07/05/2024 from: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/TA-9-2022-0326_EN.pdf

Fagerberg, J. 2001. Benchmarking: A New and Useful Tool for Policy Learning? Working Papers on Innovation Studies 20010621, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture, University of Oslo. Retrieved on 23/05/2024 from http://www.tik.uio.no/InnoWP/tik_working_paper_20010621.pdf

Fagerberg, J. 2003. The Potential of Benchmarking as a Tool for Policy Learning, The IPTS Report, 9 (71). Retrieved on 23/05/2024 from <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/76826509.pdf>

Farrell, M., Sarkki, S., Holloway, L., Weir, L., Heikkinen, H., Lépy, É., Fransala, J., Nolan, N., McGuinness, N., von Muenchhausen, S., Santacruz, M., Herrera, E., Perello, M., Vingelli, G., Farrell, T., Garces Ortiz, S., Kinsella, A., Oprea, A., Incze, L., Mikolič, S., Kuhmonen, T., Korthals Altes, W., Štastná, M., Vaishar, A., Zlock, J. 2023. D1.1 FLIARA Conceptual Framework. Retrieved on 23/12/2024 from <https://zenodo.org/records/14045102>

GENDERACTION, 2021. Gender Mainstreaming in the ESF and ERDF. Retrieved on 04/05/2024 from: https://genderaction.eu/wpcontent/uploads/2021/09/GENDERACTION_PolicyBriefs_17_ESF_ERDF.pdf

Murtagh, A., Farrell, M. and Weir, L. 2024a. D1.3: Assessment of Rural and Farming Policy and Legal Frameworks in relation to Women-led Innovation. Retrieved on 23/12/2024 from <https://zenodo.org/records/14045163>

Murtagh, A., Farrell, M. and Weir, L. 2024b. D1.5: Initial Guidelines for Policy Benchmarking Retrieved on 23/12/2024 from <https://zenodo.org/records/14045204>

Padel, A., Pieper, J.L., Edebohls, I. and von Davier, Z. 2022. Women on agricultural holdings in Germany: Findings and recommendations of the nationwide study “women.life.agriculture”. Policy Brief. Retrieved on 23/12/2024 from: <https://www.bmel.de/SharedDocs/Downloads/EN/Rural-Regions/women-life-agriculture-policy-brief.html>

Sivini, S., Roos, A. and Leonardelli, I. 2024. D.3.3: Women-led Innovations in Agriculture and Rural Areas, Lessons Learned Report and Fact Sheets on Female Innovations. Retrieved on 23/12/2024 from <https://zenodo.org/records/14045390>

Weir, L., Farrell, M., Murtagh, A., Martinez, V., Crowley, D., Oprea, A., Korthals Altes, W. and Kang, V. D4.1: Strategic Action Plan. Retrieved on 23/12/2024 from: <https://zenodo.org/records/14045414>

ANNEX 1: FOCUS GROUP AND CASE STUDY POLICY ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

WP3 case study policy needs analysis

WP3 of the FLIARA project carried out 20 case studies in the ten FLIARA partner countries on women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. In order to systematically assess policy relevant findings a template was developed to gather information to support T4.3 (Benchmarking and Policy Design) and T5.1 (A Framework Guiding FLIARA Policy and Practice Recommendations). Both tasks draw on the results of WP3 to understand the current situation in relation to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas to shape FLIARA policy improvements in different ways (benchmarking, participatory scenario development). The assessment template used the PESTE (Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Environmental) framework to understand the key barriers and opportunities facing women-led innovation in farming and rural areas of relevance for policy. For more detail see FLIARA's Conceptual Framework (D1.1) and Concept Note No. 23. The PESTE framework also has variations with sometimes 'Legal' also added as a category. This was also added into the framework for the WP3 case study policy assessment because of its potential significance in relation to identifying policy related issues from the FLIARA case studies. Further to this, we also included the wider topic of knowledge and skills, as well as an 'other' category as a result of gaps emerging when the initial PESTE framework approach was tested.

WP4 CoP focus group

The focus group came highlighted in the Grant Agreement under Work package WP4 – FLIARA CoP Network as one of the methods to implement Task 4.3 Benchmarking and Policy Design, together with subsequent workshops. The overall aim of the task is to continue the work on benchmarking EU and National Policy and Legal Frameworks by assessing the work carried out in WP1 and the results of case studies from WP3 and devising a strategy to engage participants at the four CoP Networking events via focus groups and workshops to discuss the findings and ascertain key issues to be brought forward to the policy design and assessment workshops.

There were 2 focus groups held alongside the FLIARA CoP Networking events in July 2024 in Galway, Ireland, and in September 2024, in Ljubljana, Slovenia. The strategy devised to engage the participants in the focus group activities during the in person events consisted in (1) preparation – including relevant results review from WP1 and WP3, participants distributions, logistics (note taking, facilitators), (2) implementation – delivering the focus group on site, note taking, facilitating, etc., (3) review – reporting on the activity, anatomizing and transcribing data, data analysis, concluding in the writing of this report. The work was organized collaboratively with WP1 and WP5 leads to ensure a seamless and streamlined policy input from the project.

During each event, 1.5h were allocated for 50% of the participants to participate in the focus group (the focus group happened concomitantly with another activity from WP5).

At each event there were 4 tables organized, each with a note taker and facilitator from the Consortium. They received a focus group guide and template to collect data, participated in a preparatory meeting, as well relevant information about participants. The activity happened in English and the data was transcribed and verified, being then centralized by T4.3 lead. At each table there were between 4 and 8 active participants in the discussion. In total, 43 people participated in the two focus groups, with over 16 Consortium members supporting (including the Ethics guardian).

To ensure relevant and correct data collection as well as to respond to the specific objective of WP4 of facilitating multi-actor engagement via the series of activities with all relevant key stakeholders, particular attention was paid to the distribution of participants. The two FLIARA CoP Networking events counted with the participation of FLIARA Ambassadors, women innovators from the county, representatives of national and EU decision-making institutions, researchers, and media (roughly 80 participants in total for each of the two events). As such, they were distributed so that at each table each type of participant was represented, taking into consideration the topics of the projects as well as the language limitation of the participants whenever possible.

All transcripts from the 8 tables were processed in digital format. The data set was combined in excel for a better analysis: labeling, identifying main topics, with the analysis itself with the conclusions being presented in this report.

ANNEX 2: INITIAL GOOD PRACTICE BENCHMARK STATEMENTS

Initial good practice policy benchmark statements related to supporting women-led rural and farm innovation emerging from D1.5

Goal	Initial good practice benchmarks
<p>Close gender gaps in farming and the rural labour market</p> <p>Achieve equal participation in rural and farm innovation</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Women are a target group in rural and farm policy ✓ Rural and farm policy include specific measures for achieving gender equality ✓ Supports for rural and farm innovation are not uncertain or volatile. ✓ Supports for rural and farm innovation address the specific disadvantages women face. ✓ Supports for rural and farm innovation harness underutilised or untapped areas of opportunity related to women-led innovation in farming and rural areas. ✓ Policy does not treat women as a homogenous group and targets the specific needs of particular groups of women in relation to rural and farm innovation. ✓ Policies exist that are community-led and place-based that allow for the specific needs of women in particular places to be addressed through a bottom-up approach.
<p>Achieve equal empowerment of women</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Adequate opportunities exist for women to influence the decisions that impact them. ✓ Adequate cooperation and networking opportunities exist for women supporting participation and success in women-led innovation. ✓ Adequate supports exist to build skills and innovation capacities supporting participation and success in women-led innovation. ✓ Policies address increasing the visibility of women-led innovation and challenge gender stereotypes related to work life and professions.
<p>Address gender related work-life conflicts</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Certain and stable support services exist that assist work and leisure life balance. ✓ Certain and stable supports exist that assist work and family life balance. ✓ Policies address features of professional life so that they do not discourage women's participation and success in innovation.

ANNEX 3: OPERATIONALISING A BENCHMARKING STATEMENT? ONE OUTLINE EXAMPLE

Benchmarking statement: Women are a target group in rural and farm policy	
Possible indicators	Examples of targeted measures
Young women farmers are prioritised for support as part of generational renewal measures	In Slovenia, the CAP Strategic Plan 2023-2027 intervention to support the establishment of young farmers' businesses women receive an additional 3 points in the selection criteria.
Addressing gender equality is prioritised in the selection of LAGs and Local Development Strategies	In Slovenia selection criteria for assessing Local Development Strategies awards supporting women 2 out of 16 overall points.
Policy dialogues on gender issues in rural areas and farming (led by Government) are being run and actions are being developed based on these dialogues	The Irish government have facilitated a National Dialogue on Women in Agriculture. The first National Dialogue in 2023 generated a 12-point Women in Agriculture Action Plan. The Women in Agriculture Working Group guides implementation of the action plan.
Official spaces exist where issues related to women in agriculture and rural areas are communicated to government and acted upon	In Slovenia, the Rural Women's Council is an advisory body within the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Food and provides opinions and input on key decisions relating to women in rural areas.
Supporting women's enterprise is a priority area for support as part of a wider non-targeted enterprise support scheme.	In Italy, the CAP 2023-2027 intervention on investments in agricultural holdings for diversification into non-agricultural activities supporting women's enterprise is included as a priority (alongside young people) as part of the beneficiary selection criteria.
Women-led rural entrepreneurship training programme exists	In Spain, the Rural Women Advancement Program has a focus on entrepreneurship and innovation and supports women through training and mentoring. The EIT Food programme Empowering Women in Agrifood supports early-stage women-led business develop their entrepreneurial path.
Women-led rural entrepreneurship training programme exists focused on increasing women's participation in sectors they are under-represented	In Italy as part of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan one of its female entrepreneurship programmes aims generate a female entrepreneurial culture and includes a focus on scientific and technological fields.
Women-led rural business networking supports exist	In Ireland the Women's Rural Entrepreneurial Network targets self-employed women, start-up or established women entrepreneurs. It is a

	local scheme run by LAGs in county Cork and Limerick.
Women-led rural business mentoring programme exists	ACORNS is peer-led support network for rural female entrepreneurs in Ireland. The focus is on helping nascent start-ups accelerate their establishment and development.
Support exists for women-led rural business organisations	In Slovenia the National Programme for Equal Opportunities for Women and Men includes an action on strengthening the role of women in agriculture. This helps to support organisations that assist with for example networking and knowledge provision such as the Association of Farming Women of Slovenia.
Access to finance: Innovative women-led rural enterprise grants exist (part-funding, non-repayable)	In Italy the Innovative Mountain Women's Enterprise scheme finances investment in women-led business projects with high technological and innovative content in mountain municipalities by providing a non-repayable grant for up to 70% of eligible expenses and to a maximum of €70,000.
Access to finance: Higher grant rates are available to rural women (part-funding, non-repayable) as part of a wider support scheme for rural business	In Ireland through the CAP the On-Farm Capital Investment Scheme supports increased farm efficiency and competitiveness by providing financial support to farmers. Grants are provided to cover 40% of costs however female and young farmers can claim 60% of the costs (up to a maximum investment ceiling).

Funded by
the European Union

Female-Led Innovation in Agriculture and Rural Areas

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

